

Research

Using hands-on activities to improve the conceptual understanding of senior high school students in electrical circuits

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Accepted: 25 November, 2019; Online: 30 December, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593562>

Abstract : This research work sought to improve the conceptual understanding of students through the use of hands-on instructional approaches in electrical circuits. Second Year General Art Four Students of John Evans Atta- Mills Senior High School numbering 57 was the sample used for the study. The research instruments used included observation, interview, questionnaires and tests. It was observed that these students believed that, the content of electrical circuits is difficult and boring, also the concept was always taught without practical activities (hands-on activities) hence the poor conceptual understanding of students and also facilitate no attempt to excel in the subject. The students were engaged in hands-on activities, group work and constant use of teaching and learning materials to develop and sustain their interest in the subject. It was deduced that the lack of activities involving learners affected their conceptual understanding and performance in integrated science. It is hoped that learners will be more engaged in the teaching and learning process through the use of hands-on activities to help improve the conceptual understanding and also to develop and sustain their interest in the subject matter.

Keywords: Hands-on activities, conceptual understanding, electrical circuits

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Overview

This introductory chapter gives a brief background to the study. It presents the statement of the problem, the purpose and significance of the study. The chapter also looks at the research questions, limitations of the study and finally the delimitation of the study.

1.1 Background to the Study

Studies about students' preconceptions in science before teaching and their change to the scientific truths have frequently been encountered in the literature from the 70s till now (Duit & Treagust, 2009). Science educators gave an importance to the studies about conceptual change because of the fact that students' ideas prior to teaching contradicted with the scientific truths, shown to be difficult to change those ideas with traditional teaching methods and created problems in the learning of new topics.

Physics is a discipline that is being applied in various fields of science. These fields include Chemistry, Biology, Agriculture and Information Communication Technology. All the above mentioned subjects are practical-oriented and therefore they are very difficult for students to understand when not taught using practical methods and activities. The subject in its nature is full of practical activities which when handled with professionalism makes it easy for students to comprehend and hence build students' interest in the subject. Most physics teachers in schools focus more on theory as opposed to finding practical ways of teaching. Majority of the blame is attributed to the lack of teaching and learning materials for the subject.

However due to the theoretical approach that has been adopted by teachers, many students find it hard to grasp even the basic concepts of the subject. Teaching and Learning materials and practical activities are therefore necessary to help students build critical thinking and self-confidence in the subject. This research documentation will

investigate ways to improve the conceptual understanding of electrical circuits in schools by presenting improvisation and other hands-on activities that can be used in and outside the classroom. Science education in Ghana is designed to equip learners with skills and scientific principles (Mereku, Yidana, Hordzi, Tete-Mensah, Tete-Mensah, & Williams , 2009). This skill could be applied to solve problems in everyday life. Physics being an aspect of science is also aimed at equipping learners with these problem-solving skills. In order to achieve this, the subject needs to be taught in such a manner that ensures development of observational, manipulative, and practical skills in the learner. Observational and identification skills involve keeping the eyes and ears opened at all times and never failing to register or draw what one has heard or seen during practical work (Osborne, 2004).

One of the essential elements in effective understanding of the electrical and electronic circuits is for students to first identify components which constitute the electric circuit and their arrangement in the circuit. In order for the students to understand the operation of the circuit and the procedures for troubleshooting and repair, he or she must be able to identify components and understand how they function within that particular circuit. He or she must also be able to trace signals through and between circuits. Manipulative skills being developed will also assist the child to move, arrange or operate for example the voltmeter using the hands to operate and take measurements during practical sessions.

Integrated science as a subject has been made compulsory for all Ghanaian students to obtain the most essential and a basic idea in Science, which is needed to help the nation to develop to its fullest potential (CRDD, 2007), Science is compulsory in most countries. This is to enable young people develop scientific understanding of their society and the associated processes, to be able to contribute to debate and make informed personal decisions. The essential outcomes of science education are to enable students to:

- develop a deeper understanding of the world around us and to be able to engage in relevant discourse about science in everyday life.
- be able to explain the relation between the rapid changes which occur in the immediate environment and the nation as a whole.
- understand some basic science concepts and the environment (Balla, Biggs, Gibson, & Chang, 1990).

In spite of whatever commitments the science educators might make, the teacher's role remain paramount in trying to achieve the aims of this laudable policy.

Many research findings have shown that Secondary School Students exhibit dwindling interest in science subjects (Esiobu, 2005). Afuwape and Olatoye (2004) cited by Oludipe (2011) reported that researches on the reasons for the lack of interest in science among students included: lack of qualified teachers, lack of practical works, insufficient allotment of time for Integrated Science on the school time-table and poor method of teaching and non/poor use of instructional materials. These he maintained were among the major factors militating against the successful implementation of the core curriculum in science. In the teaching and learning of science, a clear understanding of the concepts taught is vital. Thus for students to understand the concepts well, the teaching methods must aim at facilitating intellectual understanding of science as a subject. Learning on the other hand, is concerned with positive changes in the learner's behaviour as a result of teaching experience. Series of observations made during physics practical lessons held by some permanent and temporary physics teachers in Atta Mills Senior High School revealed that students had no idea of what they were doing or what to even make out of the circuit components arranged before them.

Also, students' scores in the final examinations were woefully below 50% and according to the chief examiner's reports over the years, from 2006 to 2012 attributed these poor performances of the students to the lack of basic skills such as improper observation, manipulation, identification and interpretation of circuit diagrams during their practical examinations (WAEC, 2012)

In addition, during my series of observations students unanimously stated that they are not taught how to identify circuit diagrams and to interpret them as required of them. In fact, they singled out the didactic or lecture method of teaching and sometimes demonstration method of teaching where they are shown the diagrams from afar and so it becomes difficult for them to identify the circuit components when placed before them. An important aspect of the transmission of knowledge in schools is through teaching. Teachers are the primary agents of curriculum implementation. Regardless of how explicit the textbook is, or how well arranged the syllabi is, it is the actions of the teacher in the classroom that mostly affect students' understanding. Students are taught concepts without them actually understanding the basic principles of the concepts. The use of appropriate hands-on instructional approaches, relevant teaching methods, strategies and techniques in teaching would encourage students' active participation in the lessons.

Science topics that are on electrical circuits in the Senior High School should be made simple for the students by teachers slowing the teaching during practical in order for the students to identify and interpret the circuit diagrams they are studying. Teachers should serve as facilitators by directing the students as to how to identify electrical circuit components and arrange circuit diagrams, they should not wait until final before students will be hurriedly taken through some form of the identification of some circuit diagrams for their final examination.

Physics is a subject that forms part of our daily activities and therefore must be taught well for easy understanding and better management of the environment. It also aims at equipping the individuals with the skills of handling basic scientific apparatus and materials. Careful analysis of the educational system in the World indicates that, there has been inconsistency in the use of appropriate medium of instruction in the classroom (Thornberg, 2007). Although teachers are supposed to adopt and use various methods of imparting knowledge to students during teaching and learning, the demands of the integrated science syllabus make it impossible most of the time. This generates the problem of not using the appropriate methods in the teaching of science

It was observed that students exhibited lukewarm attitude towards their studies during the researcher's lessons at J.E. Atta Mills Senior High School at Ekumfi Otum in the Central Region of Ghana. Only a few students attempted assignments given to them. In any case, the performance of the few was not good enough, an indication that they either, they do not have interest or they did not understand the topic as it was taught.

As part of my pre-teaching activities at Atta-Mills Senior High School, the books of the form two students were observed. Some of their classes were also observed and some other academic records that they had were also looked at. It was realized from the observations that the performance of the students in science especially physics was nothing to write home about. But it must be emphasized that, the principal institutional mechanism for developing human skills, knowledge and attitude is the Educational System. The Educational System should be able to produce professionals such as Teachers, Doctors, Engineers and Technicians who will enhance economic and social development. But all these cannot be achieved if the environment in which the education is to take place is not conducive enough. The conditions that you live or work in and the way

they influence how you feel or how effectively you can work plays a very important role in all aspects of human endeavours especially in academic enhancement.

Over the years, science educators and researchers in science education have intensified their efforts to seek a clearer understanding of the issues involved in the declining performance of students in science. Studies indicate that research efforts have proposed various suggestions and recommendations for improving the quality of science teaching and learning in Ghanaian classrooms (Busari, 1996). However, despite the various suggestions and recommendations for improving the quality of science teaching and learning and student's achievement in secondary schools, science continues to decline. In 1987, the Junior Secondary school program was implemented nationwide by the P. N. D. C. government and by 1993; it had turned a full cycle at the senior secondary level with the final examination conducted by the West African Examinations Council (W.A.E.C) providing tracks for review and appraisal.

The program saw a sharp decline in students' performance in all the subjects country wide. The sciences were the most affected with the performance being far below average.

The report went on to give the following reasons as being responsible for the mass failure in the 2003 WASSCE examinations.

Lack of professional teachers. It appeared that most candidates did not have teachers.

Enough grounds were not covered in the syllabus

Lack of practical work during course of study. Candidates who had the opportunity of going through an appreciable amount of practical science lessons clearly felt at home with

a greater part of this paper. Such candidates had clearly developed their observational skills through doing and could readily recall such skills and relevant experiences and utilize the parts of such stock of information and experience to answer questions. Most candidates appeared not to have performed any practical work or even observed any demonstrations during the course of their study. They appeared not to have seen the basic laboratory apparatus like the microscope, volumetric flasks, burettes, pipettes, slides, models etc.

Language problem, grammatical expressions, spellings and lack of scientific expressions were also some of the causes of the poor performance (WAEC, 1993).

It is worthwhile noting that all these problems stated by the chief examiner in his report stem from the fact that, the foundations of the students in science at the J. S. S. Level was not good enough. And this can be attributed to the way they learnt science and how they were taught by their teachers.

The need to improve the quality of science teaching and learning for citizens to improve the conceptual understanding and scientific literacy to cope with the demands of science and technology growth has been the yearning of every nation in this 21st century. Such efforts have been made by researchers in the United States of America (Darling-Hammond, 1997), Australia (Goodrum, Hackling & Rennie 2001) and the United Kingdom (Millar & Osborne, 1998) by engaging the support of key stakeholders in science education. Recognizing this, the need to involve key stakeholders in science education in making the recommendations for improving the quality of science teaching and learning using the practical approach in secondary schools in Ghana as a means to helping citizens to become more scientifically literate, is a task that is widely acknowledged as important.

Learning is not discovery or construction of something new and unknown; rather it is making what others already know your own. The difference is like that between doing the complex crossword puzzle in The Mirror newspaper, and completing yesterday's crossword puzzle using the solution in today's paper, trying to understand how the answers fit the clues. In the light of this, the study seeks to investigate the main reasons why students find it difficult to understand physics concepts such as in the identification of circuit diagrams and how to use hands on activities during lessons to help them improve upon their conceptual understanding, skills in identifying circuit diagrams and to interpret them as such.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Students find it difficult to understand, identify and interpret circuit diagrams during physics practical lessons. According to the Chief Examiner's report of the West African Examinations Council, (WAEC, 2003; WAEC, 2006), in the physics paper 2, students were unable to relate features of one circuit diagram to the other. The students could not as well point out the components of a circuit diagram considered peculiar to a situation. Their power of observation was clearly poor leading to their poor performance in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination. After an analysis of the previous year's academic performance and an interview with some of the students and science teachers at John Evans Atta Mills Senior High school. It appeared to the researcher that identification and interpretation of circuit diagrams was taught perhaps in more theoretical than practical terms, by simply forcing rules on the students. The point is that, the laboratory which should be a store house of electrical circuit components for students to observe identifiable components of these circuit diagrams had no electrical circuit components. Consequently, students could not link (in practical terms) what they had learnt in class or on paper and the real circuit diagram. The researcher therefore found it

necessary to provide an intervention through the use of hands-on activities to improve students' conceptual understanding and skills in the identification and interpretation of circuit diagrams during practical activities and in testing situations.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to improve upon the conceptual understanding of students in identifying and interpreting electrical circuit diagrams during practical sections in Atta Mills Senior High School, Ekumfi Otum, in the central Region of Ghana.

1.4 Research Objectives

1. To use hands-on instructional approaches to improve upon the conceptual understanding of second year art students in integrated science.
2. To improve the conceptual understanding of students in electrical circuits by students, through the use of activity-based methods of teaching.
3. To sample the views of students in the use of hands-activities to teach electrical circuits.

1.5 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the data gathering process:

1. What difficulties do 2art4 students of Atta Mills Senior High school face in the use of hands-on activities during lessons on electrical circuits?
2. To what extent will the use of activity-based method of teaching improve upon the conceptual understanding of 2art4 students of Atta Mills Senior High school in the identification of the components and the interpretation of circuit diagrams?

3. What are the views of 2art4 students of Atta Mills Senior High school on the use of hands-on activities to teach electrical circuits?

1.6 Significance of the study.

It is hoped that the research information will be available to the physics teachers in Atta Mills Senior High School which will help them revise their teaching strategies to facilitate the conceptual understanding of students to develop their skills required to identify and interpret circuit diagrams during practical activities. It would enable students comprehend and appreciate the study of physics in Atta Mills Senior High School.

It is hoped that findings from this study could be of help to sister schools that may be facing similar difficulties.

1.7 Delimitations of the study

This study involved only form two students in Atta Mills Senior High School and two other classes (1Art 2 & 1AG) in the school.

The study also focused only on the students' ability to identify and interpret the components of electric circuits. The students' knowledge of physics topics was not tested.

1.8 Limitations of the study

Inadequate time and funds constituted constrains which limited the researcher's efforts to reach all schools in the District. Therefore, the study was conducted in Atta Mills Senior High School.

Poor record keeping and data management posed some difficulties in extracting data from the existing literature in the school and the District education office.

1.9 Definition of Terms

It is important to define some key concepts that have been used in order to clarify the context within which they are being used in this study.

Concepts refer to abstract ideas representing the fundamental characteristics of what it represents. Concepts arise as abstractions or generalizations from experience or the result of transformation of existing ideas.

Conceptual understanding refers to knowing more than the isolated facts and methods. The successful student understands mathematical ideas and has the ability to transfer their knowledge into new situations and apply it to new contexts.

Academic performance refers to a successful accomplishment or performance in a particular subject area. It is indicated as by grades, marks and scores of descriptive commentaries. It includes how students deal with their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers in a fixed time or academic year (Hawis & Hawes, 1982 cited in Dimbisso, 2009). In order to avoid monotony, different terms such as academic achievements is used in this study.

Low Academic performance refers to a situation in which the students performs below his or her potential in both class tests and subsequent WASSCE exams, resulting in low levels of knowledge acquisition that fall short of what is required to successfully complete secondary education and continue to tertiary institutions in the country.

Teacher factors refer to his/her commitment to teaching, qualification and experience, his or her mastery of the subject matter and methods of teaching. Teachers are believed to be the major source of knowledge for pupils as well as the main actors in educational curriculum implementation (Anamuah-Mensah, Asabere-Ameyaw & Dennis, 2007).

Operational definitions

Throughout the study, the following words and terminologies carried these meanings attached to them, unless otherwise stated;

Education; is a process and a series of activities which aim at enabling an individual to assimilate and develop knowledge , skills, values and understanding that are not simply related to a narrow field of activity but allow a broad based range of problems to be defined, analysed and solved.

Professional Teacher: a person who has learnt the art of imparting knowledge to others from an institution specialize in teaching methods, school administration, psychology and philosophy of education and universities which train people for the teaching service.

Ghana Education Service (**GES**)

University of Education-Winneba (**UEW**)

West Africa Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (**WASSCE**)

1.10 Organization of the thesis

The research report is presented in five chapters. The first chapter presents the background to the study, statement of the problem, research objectives and questions, significance of the study as well as limitation and delimitation of the study. Chapter two reviews the relevant literature on the use of instructional methods and materials while chapter three gives a detailed analysis on the area of study and the methodology used in the study. It discusses the population, the sample and sampling techniques, data analysis and tools used

in the study. In chapter four, the results, data collection and the data analyses are discussed in addition to the presentation on research questions. Finally, in chapter five, a summary of the major findings, conclusion and recommendations based on the interpretations and discussions of the data collected are presented.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Overview

This chapter is apportioned with examination of different teaching methods, activity-based method, hands on activities, benefits of hands-on teaching over traditional methods of teaching, Hands-on and active learning, Impact of Hands-On-Approach on Student Academic Performance, Conceptual Understanding, learning about electric circuits.

2.1 Teaching Methods

Research on concept acquisition has revealed that children learn by active interaction initially with concrete objects and later with abstract entities. In addition, Piaget has suggested that cognitive development occurs through an active involvement, an interaction of the child with objects and phenomena that leads to cognitive conflicts and subsequently to equilibration or self-regulation (Piaget, 1964). Science as a way of knowing includes a set of unique procedures or processes which are regarded as 'standard' or acceptable in generating new knowledge. This science is characterized and differentiated from other ways of knowing by the nature of its knowledge and the procedures by which new knowledge is generated. The importance of using a variety of learning modes in teaching science probably cannot be over emphasized from a <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593562> 262

psychological point of view. One of the principal causes of students' losing interest in science is the teacher's use of one method of teaching to the exclusion of all the others. The science teacher should be acquainted with the use of a variety of methods and procedures of teaching science.

According to Atiku (2004), approaches or strategies which one uses to communicate to learners in the teaching and learning processes are referred to as teaching methods. Appropriate styles which one can present a lesson are also referred to as teaching methods or styles.

Teaching methods can otherwise be described as instructional methodology, which includes all special ways through which an instructor imparts or inculcates knowledge in the learner. Such instructional methods may vary from teacher to teacher and from subject to subject. Every instructional method aims at involving the learner in meaningful activities which will result into the successful attainment of learning objectives (Talabi, 2010).

Woods (1995) cited in Erinoshio (2009) defined teaching method or style as the manner in which a teacher effectively and efficiently interacts within the classroom environment to bring about quality subject matter among students. According to Woods, there are three teaching methods identified. These are: discipline-centered, teacher-centered, and student-centered methods of teaching.

Discipline-centered method of teaching aims at the subject matter than what the teacher does. Contents of the syllabus or textbook must be covered regardless of what the student absorbs. This method is at times used in our schools as the content must be given to students before they write their final external examinations.

The teacher-centered method of teaching is also known as the 'chalk' method of teaching. The teacher acts as an authoritative expert, the main source of knowledge and the centre point of every activity in the teaching and learning process. In this teaching arena, students are passive and they merely regurgitate content. Teaching is to transmit information and help student to master facts for examination purposes. Teacher-centered methods of teaching include lectures, explanations and illustrations. This allows minimal teacher-student interactions though much information is given to students. The lecture method is mostly effective at the tertiary level of education and during introduction, demonstrations and summary of a lesson at the primary and secondary levels of education.

The learner –centered method is the most effective teaching method for creating a dynamic classroom environment. The prior concern of the teacher is how to engage student in activities so as to develop their own ideas, and share with others through collaborative work. Students are able to develop skills, have cognitive understanding of concepts. Classroom activities, instructional contents and teaching methods are selected to facilitate active learning, critical thinking, stimulate interest and promote positive attitude towards science. The teacher in this situation is a facilitator, hence he or she uses approaches that encourage flexibility and more student engagement. Learner –centered methods of teaching include, questioning, collaborative learning, cooperative learning, discussions and activity- based methods.

Many successful public speakers know that they need to tailor their message to resonate with their audience. Similarly, think about how marketers carefully research their audiences to learn more about the needs of consumers to better position their products. This process raises a series of related questions for college faculty: How well do we

know what our students already know, what their interests are, what they want to learn, and what lessons they walk away with from our teaching (Ogle, 1986)?

The best way to learn the answers to these questions is to ask them often. Instructors who use the “K-W-L technique” ask their students to list what they know, what they want to know, and what they learned each class (Ogle, 1986). These data are exceptionally helpful in adjusting the content of lessons to ensure that you meet the needs of the greatest number of students. Other classroom assessment techniques that are easy to use include asking students how the material related to them or their interests, inquiring about what remains confusing, or allowing students to provide feedback to the instructor via clickers (Angelo & Cross, 1993). These methods complement the helpfulness of frequent quizzes and written assignments that regularly monitor students’ performance.

Professors who use differentiated instruction (Chapman, Bettinger & Due 2002) give students different options during class time (e.g., students form flexible groups that have complementary tasks centering around the topic of the lesson). Similarly, students have the opportunity to select from a range of options for evaluation (e.g., research paper, oral presentation, applied project, traditional exam). This approach builds on students’ strengths and interests in learning science.

According to Dosoo (1996), it is important for teachers to know how students learn; this will enable teachers put what they want to teach in suitable ways for learning to occur easily and also to expose learners to the techniques that make learning easier. According to Mckeachie (1994), all teaching styles can stimulate learning if used appropriately, although the student- centered style leads to better retention, better problem solving, better application of knowledge and a better motivation for learning. Examples of teaching methods use in Ghanaian schools are discussion, discovery activity, lecture, brainstorming,

project, demonstration, etc. The fact that learning to “explain ideas in science” as well as to “evaluate arguments based on scientific evidence” is given little emphasis at all levels suggests that, students may be learning science without understanding of what they learn. It could also mean that science teachers are relying on teaching methods or strategies that are ineffective for promoting understanding of subject. Teaching of science in the basic and secondary schools can be made easy and interesting or difficult and boring depending upon the teacher’s approach towards teaching.

2.2 Activity-Based Method of Teaching

Activity-based method is described as a marriage between the teacher-centered and the child-centered approaches to teaching and learning. Learning by doing appears to be the best way students learn. The learner has the capacity to learning through personal actions and experience and start developing their ideas about world. They interpret things according to their own thoughts and experiences. Activity based teaching method helps them to construct their knowledge. According to (Haury & Rillero, 1994) A child best learns to swim by getting into water; likewise, a child best learns science by doing science. Doing science is not only limited to reading or hearing but it holds students in laboratory work to test ideas and develop understanding (Ewers, 2001). Hence, science-teaching plan is incomplete without science experiences.

In the activity method the teacher explains, describes, demonstrates, distributes teaching aids and gives instructions to students. On the other hand, the students perform the following activities: answering questions orally or in writing, exploring teaching aids, discussing charts or pictures, drawing and searching for information (Atiku, 2004). Teaching and learning can become more effective and easier when students learn by observing and doing an experiment. It has been explained that activity and

experimentations are ideal means of getting students acquire facts, ideas and understanding of concepts (Dewey, 1985).

Dickinson (2003) states that, the understanding of every subject is developed through the engagement of activities. Activities are designed to provide direct experience of something. Activities include practical work, and group presentation.

The teacher, aside what have been said, should be vested in the totality of planning, organizing and counselling, geared towards helping his students and creating a favourable classroom climate, performing assiduously and assessing his/her work constantly. He/she should be the director of learning, a guide, facilitator, and motivator; full of creativity and innovative ideas. In the classroom, students ought to be doing a great deal more than just listening to the teacher. Montessori (1966) found out that, the use of carefully designed play activities helped students to learn so well that, they actually excelled in public examinations. Students can be asked to design their own experiments as a means of helping them to develop positive attitudes towards the study of science.

Many students with disinterest in science leading to their low performance benefit from learning science through an activity oriented approach that reduces the reliance on textbooks, lectures, knowledge of vocabulary, and pencil and-paper tests (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 1994). This kind of approach seeks to promote learning by providing students with experiences that allow them to discover and experiment with science. Through discovery and inquiry, teachers involve students in creating and expanding their knowledge and understanding about the content area being studied (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 1995).

When employing an activities-oriented approach, teachers offer students a variety of active educational experiences structured according to a learning cycle. This cycle consists of an

instructional sequence that includes engagement, exploration, development, and extension (Guillaume, Yopp, & Yopp, 1996).

Relating science instruction to students' personal experiences and to general societal problems is an essential component of an activities-oriented approach. Relating science to practical, civic, professional, recreational, and cultural events that are familiar and relevant to students' backgrounds and experiences can promote science literacy, motivate students, and help them learn to value science. To aid students in seeing the relevance of science to their lives, teachers can present them with information, issues, and problems that relate to real-life situations and discuss with them the relevance of these problems to their lives and the situations in which this content can be applied. For example, students can investigate socially significant problems such as water supply, weather, pollution, nutrition, and solar energy.

Teachers can make connections between science and students' cultural backgrounds by using learning activities and instructional materials that;

- explore the different cultural origins of science,
- discuss scientific solutions and practices developed and used in all parts of the world,
- highlight the achievements of culturally and linguistically diverse scientists, and
 - present a range of culturally diverse practical applications.

Connections to students' lives and cultures also can be established by having students

- conduct problem-solving activities that address community-based problems,
- use artifacts, buildings, geographical sites, museums, and other resources in their community, and

- interview community members.

These experiences will help illustrate and reinforce concepts, issues, phenomena, and events (Fradd & Lee, 1995). Van der Linde (2005) contends that the lack of interest in science could be attributed to other factors including issues of poverty, resources and infrastructure of schools.

Many factors such school environment, past experience, age, teachers' personality and teaching style have been found to influence student's attitude and interest (Murphy, 1990; Ornstein, 2006).

Class field trips that are directly related to the curriculum can make learning more meaningful and real for students. They can also serve as the basis for developing instructional units. Trips to community and regional science museums and ecological sites can offer direct experiences and authentic tasks related to what students are learning. In addition, many field trips provide hands-on experiences that promote the learning not just of factual information, but also of processes. To help teachers and students benefit from field trips, many museums provide teacher training programs, model curricula and teaching strategies, special tours, exhibits, and materials for school groups and traveling exhibits that prepare students for and build upon experiences at the museum. Field trips also can be enhanced by giving students a variety of pre-trip learning experiences to prepare them, explaining expectations regarding their behavior on the trip, giving them notepads on which to take notes and make sketches, eliciting and answering questions on the ride to the site, and discussing positive and negative aspects of the trip with them on the ride back to school (Roberts & Kellough, 1996).

In activities-oriented approaches, teachers focus on breadth of understanding rather than a broad coverage of science. Carnine (1995) proposed that educators structure instruction in

science according to "big ideas," which he defined as important concepts or principles that help students organize, connect, and apply material so that they see a meaningful relationship between the material to be learned and their own lives.

The science performance of students can also be enhanced when teachers organize instruction around broad-based, common, and interdisciplinary theme concepts (Kataoka & Lock, 1995; Rutherford & Ahlgren, 1990). Interdisciplinary themes can link the various science disciplines (e.g., biology, chemistry, earth science, physics) as well as relate science themes to other subject areas (e.g., English, mathematics, social studies, foreign languages, art, music). For example, for an interdisciplinary thematic unit on weather, students would study the scientific principles undergirding various weather patterns as part of science class and the history of weather and its effects on lifestyles and cultural traditions in social studies class. This will therefore improve student performance not only in science but other subject as well.

In an activities-based approach, teachers often structure learning so that students work in cooperative learning groups (Gurganus et al., 1995). The use of such groups can encourage the establishment of scientific classroom communities where students work in groups to communicate about and experiment with solutions to scientific problems. Cooperatively structured learning lets students formulate and pose questions, share ideas, clarify thoughts, experiment, brainstorm, and present solutions with their classmates. Students can see multiple perspectives and solutions to scientific problems. For example, in a unit about flowers, students can be assigned to work in cooperative groups to design a flower garden for their school. The group can plan their garden by posing questions (What flowers grow best in the available soil and lighting conditions? What flowers and colors go together? What materials will be needed to maintain the garden?) and gathering

data to address these questions. The group also can share a drawing of their proposed garden and the reasons that guided their design with the whole class.

Group work is a form of cooperative learning which aims to develop student's knowledge, generic skills (e.g. communication skills, collaborative skills, critical thinking skills), attitude and hence increase their performance. The ability to participate effectively in group work or team work is seen as a desirable employability skill and should be considered to be part of every learner's educational experience. Group work can be a means of acknowledging and utilizing an individual learner's additional strengths and expertise. Skills required for Group Work include; teamwork, communication, problem-solving, time management, negotiation, delegation, and co-operation. These and more will students acquire when involved in group activities. Group activities or work should be done involving learners of different ethnic groups, ability and interest to solve common problems. According to Talabi (2010) group activities have the advantage of giving weak students the confidence to learn faster from colleagues than from the teacher. Students can be grouped in three ways. These are:

- Grouping students with similar ability; this is where learners are grouped according to their abilities in a particular subject.
- Grouping students with mixed ability; here learners are grouped according to their abilities in a particular subject.
- Interest grouping, which enable teachers to group learners grouped according to interest on the same topic or subject. This group can be changed from time to time.

Dickinson (2003) agreed with the view that, learners deepen and consolidate their understanding through their own performances in the teaching and learning process. As

students work to make meaning for others, they make meaning for themselves too. Group work enables students to work as teams hence promote unity and appreciation of one another among them. Students with disinterest for a particular subject develop the interest for it, when they constantly work with others who have the interest for it.

Instructional technology and interactive multimedia provide students with access to learning environments that link text, sound, animation, video, and graphics to present content in a nonlinear and instantaneous fashion that can foster critical thinking skills and social interactions (The Cognition and Technology Group at Vanderbilt Learning Technology Center, 1993). These technologies also can be incorporated throughout the curriculum to adapt instruction to students' learning styles and provide them with experiences that allow them to control their learning. Instructional technology and interactive multimedia such as computer software, hypertext/hypermedia, computer simulations, videocassettes, videodiscs, captioned television, liquid crystal display (LCD) computer projection panels, CD-ROM, virtual reality, and the the Internet can be used to introduce, review, and apply science concepts and have students experience events, places, and phenomena (Trowbridge & Bybee, 1996). For example, through virtual reality systems, students can experience Newton's law of gravity firsthand or through multimedia applications, they can perform complicated scientific experiments such as studying chemical reactions. In addition to providing students with an opportunity to obtain information about and interact with unique aspects of science, these instructional delivery systems can motivate them and stimulate their curiosity.

The Internet holds great promise as an instructional tool because it provides educators and students with access to the information superhighway and a variety of exploratory and discovery based learning and communication experiences (Peha, 1995). The Internet also can offer students greater control over the curriculum because it provides them with many

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choices related to what and how they learn. Specifically, students can learn science by having access to information, educational resources, pictorials, databases, problem-solving experiences, and communications with other students and professionals from throughout the world. For example, the National Geographic Society and the Technical Education Research Center sponsor the Kids Network, an international telecommunications-based curriculum to teach science and geography to elementary and middle school students (Bradsher & Hagan, 1995). Students work in small groups to pose questions concerning socially significant problems, conduct experiments, and collect and analyze data related to their questions. Through the network, students exchange information and share their findings with peers worldwide. Listings and descriptions of computer networking resources for educators and students are available and can be obtained by contacting professional organizations, state education departments, and computer-based companies.

According to McDermott (1996), more competent teacher, who might be able to adopt lecture method, cannot be expected to follow the activity based instruction so rapidly. In reality, teacher's uncertainty, lack of resources, material management problems, discomfort, lack of time, limited backgrounds with experiential approaches to science teaching and dependency on textbooks are the causes of using hands-on/minds on activities often than lecture and discussion (Lebuffe, 1994).

Activity-based learning (ABL) based on verity of activity based teaching methods. The prerequisite for this learning should be based on doing experiments or activities. If learner is provided the opportunity to think and solve the problems on their own, then the learning becomes long lasting. The important features of the activity-based teaching are that it is learner centered and it encourages self-learning. It also allows the learner to study according to his or her own ability and skills.

2.3 Hands-on activities in Teaching

"Hands-on activities mean students have objects (both living and inanimate) directly available for investigation" (Meinhard, 1992, p.2). Hands-on science is defined mainly as any instructional approach involving activity and direct experience with natural phenomena or any educational experience that actively involve students in manipulating objects to gain knowledge or understanding (Haury & Rillero, 1994). Some terms such as materials-centered science and activity-centered science are used synonymous with hands-on science or terms such as materials-centered activities, manipulative activities and practical activities are used synonymous with hands-on activities (Doran & Hejaily, 1992). Unlike the laboratory works, hands-on activities do not necessarily need some special equipment and special medium.

According to Ewers (2001), doing science, as opposed to simply hearing or reading about it, engages students and allows students to test their own ideas and build their own understanding. Therefore, it is difficult to imagine a science-teaching programme without doing science experiences. The doing activities that involve hand manipulations were called hands on activities.

Ekwueme, Ekon & Ezenwa-Nebife (2015) stated that Hands-on-approach is a method of instruction where students are guided to gain knowledge by experience. This means giving the students the opportunity to manipulate the objects they are studying, for instance, plants, insects, rocks, water, magnetic field, scientific instruments, calculators, rulers, mathematical set, and shapes during teaching. In fact, it is a process of doing mathematics and science where students become active participants in the classroom.

In a more general sense, it seems to mean learning by experience (Flick, 1993). There are two ways that we find the term hands-on science in common use today. The first

uses hands-on science to refer to a general approach to instruction. Hands-on science can be thought of as a philosophy guiding when and how to use the broad range of teaching strategies needed to address diversity in contemporary classrooms. The second way hands-on science is commonly used is in terms of a specific instructional strategy where students are actively engaged in manipulating materials, using called a hands-on science activity (Flick, 1993).

Elementary school mathematics teachers have long been interested in the use of manipulatives to provide concrete learning experiences (Ross & Kurtz, 1993). The Thesaurus of Eric Descriptors defines manipulative materials as instructional materials that are designed to be touched or handled by students and which develop their muscles, perceptual skills and psychomotor skills. (U.S. Department of Education, 1991).

The concept of hands-on science is predicated on the belief that a science program for elementary children should be based on the method children instinctively employ to make sense of the world around them. Science must be experienced to be understood. These experiences should allow students to be actively engaged in the manipulation of everyday objects and materials from the real world. Children are by nature observers and explorers, and the most effective approach to learning should capitalize on these intrinsic abilities (Shaply & Luttrell, 1993).

"Hands-on science is defined as any science laboratory activity that allows the student to handle, manipulate or observe a scientific process"(Lumpe & Oliver, 1991, p. 345). Hands-on teaching can be differentiated from lectures and demonstrations by the central criterion that students interact with materials to make observations, but the approach involves more than mere activity. The assumption is that direct experiences with natural phenomena will provoke curiosity and thinking, so, "recently, a new twist has been added,

and the topic is called Hands-on or Minds-on science" (Lumpe & Oliver, 1991). Teachers are now seeking to understand what students are learning as a result of busy hands. This need of involving hands in manipulating objects during teaching is being expressed through the introduction of new terms such as minds-on and hands-on science (Flick, 1993).

Hands-on learning involves the child in a total learning experience which enhances the child's ability to think critically. The child must plan a process to test a hypothesis, put the process into motion using various hands-on materials, see the process to completion, and then be able to explain the attained results. Hands-on learning is not just a fad because it enables students to become critical thinkers, able to apply not only what they have learned, but more importantly, the process of learning, to various life situations. Hands-on learning, however, is not simply manipulating things. It is engaging in in-depth investigations with objects, materials, phenomena, and ideas and drawing meaning and understanding from those experiences. Other terms for this are inquiry learning, hands-on, and minds-on learning. The importance of student investigation of basic scientific principles cannot be overstated. Hands-on learning is the only way students can directly observe and understand science. As students develop effective techniques for observing and testing everything around them, they learn the what, how, when, and why, of things with which they interact (Kren, 1979)

A hands-on approach requires students to become active participants instead of passive learners who listen to lectures or watch films. Laboratory and field activities are traditional methods of giving students hands-on experiences. With the advent of classroom technology, students can now participate in a non-traditional form of hands-on education through the use of computers. This technology extends hands-on learning to include minds-on skills.

Lumpe and Oliver (1991) classified Hands-on learning into three different dimensions: the inquiry dimension, the structure dimension, and the experimental dimension. In inquiry learning, the student uses activities to make discoveries. The structure dimension refers to the amount of guidance given to the student. If each step is detailed, this is known as a cookbook style lab. These types of activities do not increase a student's problem-solving abilities. The third dimension is the experimental dimension which involves the aspect of proving a discovery, usually through the use of a controlled experiment

2.4 Hands-on and active learning

Active learning has become an all-encompassing term that has been based largely on peoples' intuitive understanding of the term rather than any universal definition (Bromwell & Eison, 1991). To address this issue, Bromwell and Eison (1991) defined active learning as "instructional activities involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing". However, this is still a very inclusive definition that allows for a multitude of teaching methods, ranging from pausing briefly during lectures so students can discuss their notes (Ruhl, Hughes, & Schloss, 1987) to having students physically running around, playing a game (Humphrey, 1969).

Given the broad range of activities that are included under the term active learning, it is, perhaps, unsurprising that studies examining the effectiveness of active learning techniques have yielded inconsistent results. In some studies, active learning and traditional learning have been shown to yield similar outcomes (Lopata, Wallace, & Finn, 2005). In other studies, active learning has been shown to yield better outcomes than traditional learning (Mayer, 2004; Hammett, 2010), though different studies focus on different types of active learning. One distinction that has been made in the literature is between behavioral active learning and cognitive active learning. Behavioral active learning involves activities that

engage the body, such as dancing or running around; cognitive active learning, on the other hand, involves activities that engage the mind, such as class discussions and taking notes. Unfortunately, even here, recommendations are mixed; some researchers argue for a more behaviorally active approach (Hammett, 2010), while others argue for a more cognitively active approach (Mayer, 2004).

Because of these mixed results and because so many different types of active learning fall under (Bromwell & Eison, 1991) definition, no concrete conclusions about its success or failure as a whole can be drawn from the hodgepodge of research. Although researchers are working on what is nominally the same topic, they are not actually exploring the same phenomena at all (Michel, Cater, & Varela, 2009). Michel, Cater and Varela (2009) explain, “Researchers and educators are free to use a plethora of activities that qualify as active learning, making the comparison of studies very difficult. It could very well be the case that only certain aspects of what educators identify as active learning actually improve learning outcomes” (p. 414).

Because there are no clear conclusions about the success or failure of active learning as a whole, yet wide arrays of active learning techniques are used in the classroom, it is important to discover which active learning methods do work.

A type of active learning that embraces strengths of both behavioral active learning and cognitive active learning is hands-on learning (Korwin & Jones, 1990). Hands-on learning involves hands-on activities incorporated into the lesson that act as physical tools to help explain and teach a concept to students. For example, students learning verbs might be given a game piece that they would use to physically represent a given verb; if the verb was ‘jump,’ the students must make their game piece jump. The students are physically manipulating the game piece with their hands to learn verbs. Hands-on learning differs

from the more extreme behavioral types of active learning, such as playing a game of Verb Tag, in which students must enact the given verb (e.g., jump) while trying to get away from the student that is 'it.' Hands-on learning also differs from simpler cognitive types of active learning, such as discussing in class what verbs are and then having students come up with their own examples of verbs. On the active learning continuum, hands-on learning falls somewhere in the middle, located between the more extreme behavioral and cognitive types of active learning.

Hands-on learning captures positive qualities of both behavioral active learning and cognitive active learning. One positive quality of behavioral active learning that is captured in hands-on learning is that it naturally evokes more interest and enjoyment in students than cognitive active learning does. According to Humphrey (1969), "active games, because of their very nature, are more likely than traditional learning activities, to be structured in a way that the child's interest is held (p. 22)." Hands-on learning, because it involves the physical manipulation of objects, draws on the interest factor of behavioral active learning though to a lesser degree satisfying the need for behavioral engagement and thus naturally keeping students interested and involved. Supporting this theory of greater interest and enjoyment in hands-on learning, satisfaction ratings have shown that students tend to express more enjoyment and satisfaction from hands-on learning than traditional learning (Walberg, 1986).

One positive quality of cognitive active learning that is also captured in hands-on learning is that it encourages students to be more mentally engaged than behavioral active learning does. In fact, lack of mental engagement during behavioral active learning has been a common criticism against it in previous literature (Kolb, 1984). Traditional classrooms are structured in a way in which cognitive active learning is used, including such

methods as discussion, use of visual aids, etc. However, students often have short attention spans and quickly lose interest during pure cognitive active learning. Hands-on learning, though, engages students mentally as they conceptualize abstract lessons through the use of relevant concrete objects and activities. Hands-on learning, then, draws on the interest factor of behavioral active learning and the mental engagement factor of cognitive active learning, providing a more integrative, holistic approach than either of the two extremes.

Hands-on learning also captures the practicality of cognitive active learning in that it is more applicable in a typical elementary school classroom than extreme types of behavioral active learning. The setup of most elementary school classrooms does not leave a large space available for an abundance of physical activity, such as games that involve running.

However, cognitive active learning, which involves mostly sitting at a desk and actively thinking, is easily accomplished in the classroom. Like cognitive active learning, hands-on learning can be accommodated to a typical classroom because students can participate in hands-on activities while remaining at their desks or coming together in small groups. Hands-on learning incorporates the applicability of cognitive active learning, making it a practical and feasible learning approach.

Not only does hands-on learning draw on positive qualities of more extreme types of behavioral and cognitive active learning, but it also supported by Piaget's theory of the stages of cognitive development, specifically his theory that children from ages seven to twelve are in the concrete operational stage. In the concrete operational stage, children are able to "reason logically about concrete objects and events" (Siegler, Deloache, & Eisenberg, 2006).

Much of the previous literature focuses on various types of active learning, but few studies focus specifically on hands-on learning. One study that does focus on hands-on learning was done by Ward, Sadler, and Shapiro (2008), who found that hands-on learning groups significantly outperformed traditional learning groups in an astronomy curriculum. In the study by Ward et al. (2008), approximately 750 third- through sixth-grade students were assigned as the hands-on group. Using the Astronomy Resources for Inter curricular Elementary Science (ARIES) curriculum, they participated in hands-on activities relating to exploring the concepts of time, light and color, and the earth in motion. Approximately 650 fourth- through sixth-grade students were assigned as the traditional group; they were taught the same three topics using traditional methods. Results showed that students in the hands-on ARIES group performed significantly better on post-tests, which consisted of open-ended questions about the topics covered, than students in the traditional group (Ward, Sadler, & Shapiro, 2008). This study suggests that hands-on learning is more beneficial than traditional learning and therefore provides support for the implementation of hands-on activities into the traditional classroom curriculum.

2.5 Impact of Hands-On-Approach on Student Academic Performance

Several studies in the literature show that hands-on activities help students to outperform students who follow traditional, text-based programmes (Turpin, 2000). Hands-on activities enhance students conceptual understanding and replace their misconceptions with the scientific ones (Ünal, 2008), develop students attitudes toward science positively (Bilgin, 2006) and encourage their creativity in problem solving, promote student independence, improves skills such as reading, arithmetic computation, and communication (Haury & Rillero, 1994). Lebuffe (1994) emphasized that children learn better when they can touch,

feel, measure, manipulate, draw, and make charts, record data and when they find answers for themselves rather than being given the answer in a textbook or lecture.

Ekwueme, Ekon and Ezenwa-Nebife (2015) posit that hands-on learning approach involves the child in a total learning experience which enhances the child's ability to think critically. It is obvious therefore, that any teaching strategy that is skewed towards this direction can be seen as an activity-oriented teaching method (Hands-on-approach).

Hands-on-approach has been proposed as a means to increase students' academic achievement and conceptual understanding of scientific concepts by manipulating objects which may make abstract knowledge more concrete and clearer. Through hands-on-approach, students are able to engage in real life illustrations and observe the effects of changes in different variables. It offers concrete illustrations of concepts. This method is learner-centered which allows the learner to see, touch and manipulate objects while learning as mathematics are more of seeing and doing than hearing; so also with science that advocates "do it yourself"(Ekwueme, Ekon & Ezenwa-Nebife, 2015)

Obanya (2012) in his convocation lecture confirmed the above statement by adding that the average retention rate of learning by lecture is 5% while that of practice by doing (Activity-oriented) is about 75%. It can be seen that retention rate increases progressively with the use of more interactive and activity-oriented teaching methods. On the contrary, Ekwueme and Meremikwu (2010) observed in their study that some teachers object to the use of interactive activity-oriented method stating that it is time consuming and do not permit total coverage of the syllabus.

Hands on activities develop critical thinking skills. By investigating the subject matter through hands-on activities, students learn both content and thinking strategies
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(Hmelo-Silver, 2004). Hands-on activities support problem-based approaches to learning by focusing on the experience and process of investigating, proposing and creating solutions. As a result, students learn how to gather information and solve problems.

Hands on activities encourage communication and builds language skills. Hands-on activities use real objects to support multiple modes of communication, linking visual learning to what is being said and discussed (Lee, Penfield & Maerten-Rivera, 2009). Hands-on activities enable students to discuss debate, verbalize and explain processes and concepts while working together. An observation of hands-on learning noted that students' demonstrated strong communication tied to working in teams (Bass, Yumol, &Hazer, 2011).

Bass, Yumol and Hazer (2011) opined that with the right kind of planning and presentation, hands-on teaching can restore focus and spark engagement. An independent observation of teachers using hands-on learning noted that students were enthusiastic and generally stayed on-task during guided hands-on activities.

It has been demonstrated that students who are disadvantaged economically or academically gain the most from activity-based programmes (Bredderman, 2012). Every learner is provided with the same materials and guidance, and can interact with the lessons in the way that builds on their unique level of prior knowledge, past experiences and current abilities. Hands-on learning inspires all students to meet and exceed high standards for learning and participation, while engaging multiple senses (sight, sound, touch, etc.). The learner can interact with 4 Inspiring Hands-On Learning the materials in a way that makes sense for them (e.g., students who tend to learn visually may connect with the colors and sights while tactile learners can appreciate being able to manipulate objects).

2.6 Benefits of Hands-on Teaching

Business leaders regularly complain that our education system fails to teach students the 21st-century skills they need for the work world, such as problem-solving, communication, and the ability to work well in teams (Casner-Lotto & Barrington, 2006). In the course of doing a hands-on project, students learn to work well with other team members who may have different socioeconomic backgrounds, different learning styles, and different cultures. As a result, students are better prepared to take their place in the business world.

The benefits for educators are also numerous. For example, professional development workshops that stress hands-on learning are significantly more successful in improving teacher confidence in math and science instruction (Basista & Mathews, 2002).

Hands-on activities help teachers cut the time needed for remediation, improve classroom management by unifying students around a common organized activity, and foster a greater interpersonal and supportive emotional connection with students through sharing the process of learning with them (rather than one-way lecturing) and makes teaching and learning fun.

Hands-on teaching rekindles the sense of wonder and love of learning that young children inherently bring to the classroom. When more teachers are equipped to close the engagement gap restoring motivation, connection, and the desire to learn student conceptual understanding and performance will reach new heights and the achievement gap will become a thing of the past.

Ates and Eryilmaz (2011) stated that hands-on or minds-on activities are effective means of increasing physics achievements about simple electric circuits. Students instructed those gain a higher achievement in physics. However the hands-on or minds-on activities do not
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increase students' attitude towards simple electric circuits significantly more than the traditional method of teaching.

2.6 General issues which may hinder learning of electric circuits

A lot of research has been conducted in this area, over the past years, showing researchers' interests to improve the teaching and learning of electric circuits. This research corroborates my professional knowledge that this is a difficult topic for many students. The research has identified some specific learning challenges for students, and has suggested some teaching approaches that might help to overcome them. Yet, in spite of this, many people still readily admit that their understanding of circuits is not deep, even after instruction. If students are just trained to use equations to solve numerical examples, and to recall information to get them through an examination, then providing qualitative explanations to questions dealing with circuits becomes difficult (Mazur, 1997). Often, retention of the learnt material is poor (Fleer, 1994), even if students manage to pass examinations. Such occurrences should make all educators think about whether we are actually teaching students to counterfeit understanding. While this may be said with reference to all topics, it seems even more relevant when abstract concepts are involved, and when learners do not easily relate with scientific mental representations.

Another point which cannot be ignored but which is, unfortunately, often sidelined by teachers, perhaps due to time constraints in covering the syllabus, is that young students come to class with pre-instruction ideas which are heavily influenced by previous personal experience. At the same time, older students may come with partly remembered ideas from earlier years. We know that to be meaningful, new information must be linked to existing schema. (Ausubel, 1968) claims: "The most

important single factor influencing learning is what the learner already knows. Ascertain this and teach him accordingly in referring to the learning of mechanics, also claim that students' initial knowledge has a large influence on students' performance in physics. There is a clear indication, therefore, that students' initial knowledge has to be taken into account during instruction. This, however, can only be done effectively when teachers are aware of the ideas students hold, and know what to do to improve learning. (Aguirre, 1988) point towards the need for teachers' awareness of students' alternative conceptions, to be able to design effective instructional strategies. Yet, how far are teachers aware of students' alternative ideas related to circuits? How far is research used to inform practice?

Reflecting on these questions, while knowing of the persistent problems with students' understanding, indicated the need for more systematic research aimed both at helping students with their understanding in this area and at offering teachers a unified approach which may make their teaching more effective.

2.7 Key ideas needed to understand how electric circuits work

One of the most basic ideas required for the understanding of how the simple electric circuit operates concerns what constitutes an electric current in a closed loop. Understanding how current is generated in the circuit is also important. Resistance and how it controls the current together with the battery must be understood. Furthermore, students are expected to be able to grasp the meaning of p.d./voltage. They must acknowledge that, while there can be no current without having a p.d. across the battery terminals, it is when the current flows that a p.d. is established across resistors in the circuit.

On top of all this, these separate ideas have to be amalgamated, so that the circuit can be viewed as a system, where all the parts are working together, with changes made to one part of the circuit affecting the system as a whole. These key ideas are expected to develop as teaching progresses and as students reflect about what they are taught and what they may observe during demonstrations, practical sessions, and indeed even during everyday life experiences.

2.8 Identification of the Components of Circuit Diagrams

Identification may be considered an ability to recognize something that you have seen before. However in physics, identification is the ability to recognize a circuit diagram. Circuit diagram refers to a path in which electrons from a voltage or current flows in a closed path. The point where electrons enter the circuit is called the source of electrons. The point where electrons leave an electrical circuit is called return or earth ground. Therefore, identification of circuit diagrams can be defined as the process of recognizing the components, symbols and functions of a circuit diagram.

2.9 The Significance of the Identification of the Components Electrical Circuit Diagrams

Identification of circuit diagrams whether assembled in the laboratory or manufactured in the industry is very important. It helps one to have the details of the electronic or electrical circuit diagram. For the fire control systems repairer, this often means the

adjustment, replacement, or repair of the electrical and electronic components within the fire control instruments and their associated test equipment. In order for the student to understand the operation of the equipment and the procedures for troubleshooting and repair of the circuit.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Overview

This chapter discusses the research design, population, the sample size, research instruments and the procedures which were adopted to effectively address the problem of low conceptual understanding of students. It includes pre-intervention activities, intervention design and implementation and the post- intervention activities. The chapter also examines the validity and reliability of the instruments and methods of data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The study is an action research designed to improve students' conceptual understanding in electrical circuit. Action research, or what Hopkins (2008) prefers to call 'classroom research by teachers', was thus the best way to address students challenges in the classroom. Moreover, action research would allow for the possibility of the research plan to be flexibly revised, after reflecting on the results obtained through the cycles of the study, leading to further action-on-reflection (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2001; Hopkins, 2008). Action research is a systematic inquiry conducted by teacher researchers to gather information about the ways that a particular school operates, how they teach, and how their students' learn (Hopkins, 2008). The researcher engaged the students involved in a series of Hands-on and instruction activities to enhance their conceptual understanding in electrical circuit. The main instruments used for the study were Class test, exercises, questionnaire and interview. Class test and exercises were

conducted to evaluate students' conceptual understanding while interview was conducted to solicit students' views on the effectiveness of the intervention strategies used for the study.

3.2 Population

The target population of the study comprised 180 students, Sixty students each from the second year General Arts 4 and General Art 3 Classes as well as the second year Art 2 Class of the John Evans Atta Mills Senior High School. John Evans Atta Mills Senior High School offers four (4) different programmes namely, General Science, General Arts, Business and General Agriculture. The student population of the school was eight hundred and twelve (812). All the 812 students offer integrated science since it is a compulsory subject. Table 1 shows the breakdown of the student population in the school.

Table 1

Student Population in John Evans Atta Mills Senior High School

FORM	TOTAL NUMBER OF CLASSES	BOYS	GIRLS	TOTAL
ONE	1	110	130	240
TWO	7	130	215	345
THREE	5	117	110	227
TOTAL	13	357	455	812

3.3 Sample

Sixty (60) students were sampled from three classes with a population of 180 students due to time and for effective supervision. This size was also considered due to financial constraints and resource availability.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Purposive sampling technique was used to select Arts 2, Arts 3 and Arts 4 classes, since the problem at stake was more associated to these students. Sixty (60) of these students were randomly selected by writing 'Yes' or 'No' on pieces of paper. The pieces of paper were folded and put in a box. Pick and replace method was used. Students were asked to pick in turns and students who picked 'Yes' were used as the sample for the study.

3.5 Instrumentation

Four instruments were employed to gather data in this study. These were observation, questionnaire, diagnostic practical test and interview. The interview was used to get the general view of the students to ascertain the effectiveness of the intervention. The test was used in soliciting student's previous knowledge about identification and interpretation of electrical circuit diagrams. The diagnostic practical tests were series of identification activities designed to identify student's strength and weaknesses in identification and interpretation of electrical circuits.

3.5.1 Observation

Observation is a non- test technique which involves an action or process of closely observing or monitoring, or a comment based on something one has seen, heard or noticed (Eshun & Effrim, 2009). Students were observed during integrated science lessons as observation deals with an overt behaviour which can be seen and studied as students repeat it over a period of time.

3.5.2 Interview

Interview is a conversation where questions are asked and answers are given. In common parlance, the word “interview” refers to one-on-one conversation with one person acting in the role of the *interviewer* and the other in the role of the *interviewee*. The interviewer asks questions, the interviewee responds, with participants taking turns talking (Kvale & Brinkman, 2008).

A separate semi-structured interviews were conducted with the students. Interview was employed to find out factors that contribute to the problems students face in the learning of electrical circuits. Thirty (30) students selected at random were interviewed one after the other, about their conceptual understanding of electrical circuits.

3.5.3 Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. Although they are often designed for statistical analysis of the responses, this is not always the case. Questionnaires can be used to examine the general characteristics of a population, to compare attitudes of different groups, and to test theories (Foddy, 1994).

A questionnaire is best used to collect data when a large scale of research in literate population is concerned. A questionnaire can be in the form of closed or open ends. The closed questionnaire consists of prepared list of concrete questions and a choice of possible answers. The open-end questionnaire permits the respondents to answer freely and fully in their own words or frame of reference.

It was important to find out the student's performance towards science and in particular, approaches used in the teaching and learning of electrical circuits. The questionnaire had ten structured items. This was used to solicit responses and to code responses quickly. The questionnaire was designed and distributed in such a way that the identification of the respondents was not disclosed to ensure their full cooperation and sincere responses. Form three General Art four students were chosen to respond to the questionnaire before and during intervention. A sample of the questionnaire is presented in Appendix B.

3.6 Diagnostic Practical Test

The diagnostic practical test is designed to test the knowledge of physics that you retained from your last course and challenges that require intervention; however it is also designed to see that you have a working knowledge of the content in electrical circuits

3.6.0 Physics diagnostic test

Once the reason for conducting this research was clear, it was important to plan the strategy that would be adopted to select appropriate instruments for the study. This included decisions to be taken on which method and instruments would best fit the purpose of the research, as well as decisions on a time frame for data collection. Students' understanding of key concepts in electricity, before the beginning of the course had to be gauged. It was thus decided that a Physics Diagnostic Pre-Test would be prepared, based on ideas about circuits which students had already covered.

This test would be administered to the students groups at the start of the term. The <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593562> 293

idea was that questions would be asked about very basic concepts in electrical circuits. Moreover, as much as possible, questions would be clearly stated, probing one idea only. This would help make the interpretation of students' answers easier to handle (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2001).

The preparation of a post-test to be administered immediately after instruction was also envisaged, to see by how far and in what ways students had changed their ideas, if at all, also indicating how effective the teaching programme was in promoting learning and conceptual understanding. Questions from the pre-test which students would find difficult would be asked again, in addition to other questions on work which would be covered through the course which it did not make sense to probe in the pre-test. A delayed post-test was also planned to see by how far students retain the knowledge gained. This would be administered about one month after the post-test and would consist of similar but not same questions asked in the post-test.

3.6.1 Decision on question choice for the diagnostic testing

The following question was used to guide the planning of the questions which were deemed important to be asked in the tests:

‘What will be expected of students who have been taught electrical circuits at senior High School?’

Reflecting on this question, while also being guided by the syllabus that the students cover at each level, and ideas students have been shown to hold through previous studies mentioned in the literature review, helped in making sound decisions. The following are items which were important to probe:

- the models of current which students use;

- knowing whether electric charges constituting the current are only present in the battery or whether they are everywhere and start moving because of the presence of the battery, in a complete circuit (this is a microscopic view which students may find difficulty with but it is a very crucial point which students need to understand, if they are to understand circuits at all);
- the division of current at a junction depending on the resistances within the respective branches;
- knowing that it is not the battery alone which controls the current;
- knowing that the current through a larger resistance will be smaller.
- the effect on the current for adding resistance of resistors in series;
- the effect on the current in the main circuit, of adding resistors in parallel;
- whether it is the potential difference (p.d.) which gives rise to the current or vice versa;
- the models held by students about p.d. in series circuit. (is p.d. across series resistors additive? Does p.d. exist across the resistors and/or connecting wires? Does each resistor in a series circuit have the total p.d. of the battery across it?);
- the effect on the current of increasing the p.d. across the battery (battery p.d. shown numerically);
- the role of batteries connected in series (This item would look at the same idea as the previous one without stating the p.d. numerically);

- the models held of p.d. in parallel circuits. (Is the p.d. across resistors in parallel additive and in total equal to the p.d. across the battery? Is the p.d. across equal resistors in parallel equal to the p.d. across the battery divided by the number of resistors? What happens to the current within a parallel branch, when resistance is changed within other branches?);
- the role of batteries connected in parallel;
- the differentiation of current and p.d. (is there a current in an open circuit, even if a voltmeter reads the p.d. across the battery? Is there a p.d. across an open switch, when no current is flowing? Do the rules which apply to currents in circuits, also apply to p.d. across various points within circuits?).

Diagnostic questions from the Evidence-based Practice in Science Education (EPSE) project (Millar, Leach, Osborne, & Ratcliffe, 2006) based on current electricity were deemed appropriate for the diagnostic testing envisaged. Having access to the entire bank of questions developed in this topic made it possible to choose a set of questions to adequately probe students' understanding. Most of these questions are of the two-tier multiple choice type, requesting an answer and a reason for it. The reason is either prompted in a multiple choice set of answers or required as an open-ended response. (Tsai, Chen, Chou & Lain, 2007) claim that "many science educators have used two-tier instruments to diagnose students' alternative conceptions and reported reliable results". Moreover, it was important for this study to be supported by qualitative reasons students base their answers upon because scientifically valid causal reasoning which supports and explains an answer is an indication of deep understanding (Lee & Law, 2001). Grotzer and Perkins (2000a) refer to and acknowledge "a paucity of causal models in students' understanding" and "shallow explanations" which students usually

offer when understanding in science is probed. Thus, only by dealing with students' reasons for their answers could the probing of ideas lead to some indication of students' ideas and their understanding.

Two test items, pre-intervention and post-intervention were conducted. The two tests were of the same difficulty level as they required similar skills to execute them. Both tests were criterion-referenced test. With the criterion-referenced test, scores of a student are not compared to those of other students but rather requires the student to fulfill a given set of criteria or a pre-established standard (Eshun & Effrim, 2009). This type of test was chosen to find out exactly what a student has learnt, i.e. what a student can and cannot do as an individual. The pre- intervention test was administered in the eighth week of the first term.

The post-intervention test was conducted after the intervention activities were implemented; this was in the sixth week of the second term. This was to find out the effectiveness of the intervention. The same items were repeated but with different numbers assigned. The test was made up of two parts; the first part asked for introductory information about the student's personal data such as number (i.e. students were given identification numbers for the purpose of the study instead of names to ensure confidentiality), class and date; and the second part consisted of five multiple-choice items and section B. Each multiple-choice item had a stem with four options: one correct answer and three possible distracters.

Electrical circuit components were given to each student. They were given instructional sheets with a simple electrical circuit diagrams that demanded them to identify, examine and construct the circuit diagram on the instruction sheet. The researcher went round and

took notice of the identification that the students have done and the various circuits that they have built.

The researcher also took a critical look at the features of the circuits assembled by the students to ascertain if the students had been able to examine the circuit diagram on the instructional sheets. The circuits were collected after forty (40) minutes and marked. The pass marks of all the tests were 15 out of 20 representing 60% of the total marks. The marks scored by students were recorded after both tests.

3.7 Data Collection Procedure

Permission was sought from the Head of Department and initial visit was made to the classes. The purpose of the study was explained to the students and arrangement was made for the data collection. Students were assured of anonymity and confidentiality of their responses. They were asked not to write their names on the questionnaires. The items were explained to the students to take care of poor mastery of the English language.

The researcher with the assistance of one of the physics teachers administered fifty-seven (57) questionnaires to students of form three General Art four class. The researcher took time to explain the items to students for the purpose of clarity to minimize ambiguity with regard to their responses. The questionnaire lasted for 30 minutes and was collected back. The physics teacher and the head of science department were engaged in semi-structured interviews. Diary notes were taken to cover additional behaviours raised by students during classroom observations and interviews.

3.8 Pre-intervention

Pre-intervention exercise was taken during the diagnostic practical test. This test was aimed at consolidating the researcher's views about the problems students face when it comes to identification of circuit diagrams. Students were taken through a practical work on identification of electrical circuit. These were the instructions given to them during the practical session;

Observe and examine the electrical circuit components before you.

Describe the circuit diagram on the sheet as you see it.

Construct the circuit diagram using the components.

Outline the functions of each component.

What type connection is that?

The following weaknesses were identified;

Students did not examine the electrical components as required of them.

Students did not describe the circuit as they saw it.

Most could not construct the electrical circuit.

They could not provide the functions of some of the circuit components.

Most could not identify the type of connection it was. They wrote parallel instead of series.

3.9 Intervention

Three section activity (Sections A, B and C) were designed to correct the weaknesses identified in the identification and interpretation of circuit diagrams during the diagnostic practical exercise.

Section A dealt with the preparation needed before the start of the identification exercise.

Section B was about the skills the students needed in order to identify and construct circuit diagrams placed before them.

Section C involved the activities to help the students to identify and classify electrical circuit diagrams.

3.9.1 Intervention Design

A final means of describing an electric circuit is by use of conventional circuit symbols to provide a schematic diagram of the circuit and its components. Some circuit symbols used in schematic diagrams are shown below.

Describing Circuits with Words

Describing Circuits with

Drawings

"A circuit contains a

light bulb and a 1.5-Volt D-cell."

Description with Words: Three D-cells are placed in a battery pack to power a circuit containing three light bulbs.

Drawing of Circuit

Schematic Diagram of Circuit

Types of Circuit Connection

Two or more electrical devices in a circuit can be connected by series or parallel connections.

3.9.2 Series Circuits

When all the devices are connected using series connections, the circuit is referred to as a series circuit. In a series circuit, each device is connected in a manner such that there is only one pathway by which charge can traverse the external circuit. Each charge passing through the loop of the external circuit will pass through each resistor in consecutive fashion.

Equivalent Resistance

3.9.3 Parallel Circuits

When all the devices are connected using parallel connection, the circuit is referred to as a parallel circuit. In a parallel circuit, each device is placed in its own separate branch. The presence of branch lines means that there are multiple pathways by which charge can traverse the external circuit. Each charge passing through the loop of the external circuit will pass through a single resistor present in a single branch. When arriving at the branching location or node, a charge makes a choice as to which branch to travel through on its journey back to the low potential terminal.

3.10 Intervention Implementation

3.10.1 Section A: Preparation for Identification Exercise

Students were put into groups of two (2) for easy supervision. Students were then provided with connecting wires, switch, dry cell or battery, bulbs resistors and variety of circuit diagram sheets. Also, students were provided with a simple electric circuit to just examine.

3.10.2 Section B: Skills for Identification and Assembling

Students were taken through series of activities to equip them with the skills techniques they needed to identify and assemble electric circuit components. Such skills include being able to observe the sample circuit diagram, detect differences between the circuit diagrams provided, how to connect wires, how to position components rightly and how to look for the difference.

3.10.3 Section C: Activities Involved in Identification

The students were taken through lessons on how to identify circuit diagrams, that is, to look for the components and symbols with the naked eyes which permit quick identification. The students were also reminded of how to connect wires and circuit components, which will determine whether the circuit is in parallel or series. The students were then asked under the supervision of the researcher to identify and classify the circuit diagrams given them using the instruction above.

Apart from the above instructions, the following were done on the students' activities.

The students were taken to the school's physics laboratory for them to identify and classify the components of electrical circuits and give the functions of the components they identify.

Activities done by the students were marked and necessary corrections made.

Follow-up of identification and interpretation of electrical circuits were also made on variety of circuit diagrams and these were promptly marked.

Records of the students were kept through evaluation of their works and observation during practical lessons.

3.11 Implementation of the Intervention Activities

Hands-on instructional approaches were the main teaching strategies used during the intervention to improve the conceptual understanding of students in order to help them understand, develop interest in integrated science and also perform well in the subject. Hands-on instructional approach involves the use of teaching and learning materials (TLMs), group work or activities, presentation and practical works. TLMs used included diagrams, picture illustrations, electrical circuit components, measuring instruments and concrete materials to clearly convey meaning in a way that look real. The materials were able to help demonstrate and better explain ideas and concepts which baffled the minds of the students. These were to help develop a positive attitude towards in electrical circuits and to improve their low conceptual understanding about electrical circuits.

Group work or activity was used during electrical circuit lessons. Students of different levels of learning ability were put in groups of two or more. They performed activities to find out things for themselves and for others. This helped them to share ideas through discussions for their own understanding. In this process, facilitating of activities offered guidance and the assistance to the various groups. Comments, opinions and views which were brought forth by their own colleagues were discussed.

Sometimes students were taken out of their classroom to the science laboratory or field trips to explore ideas for their own understanding. A lot of practical activities

were conducted in which students were always involved. This ensured maximum participation by all students. They were given guide sheets containing instructions on how to carry out activities during practical or field lessons. Before the practical activities started, students had lessons on identification and interpretation as well as the use of laboratory measuring instruments and equipment/apparatus in electric circuits.

Students were given topics to write short notes on. Students were called in turns by random sampling to the chalkboard to explain their findings, lead discussions, and also assist the group in finding solutions to the various problems or difficult concepts that they could not grasp. This was to help them access information on their own, and also explain the notes to the class with confidence during presentation.

The performance of Form Three Art four students in integrated science, improved when they were made to try their hands on many exercises in the textbooks and practical workbooks either in groups or individually in the form of projects, exercises or class tests. Students were given either class exercises or assignments after every lesson. Furthermore, class tests and project works were organized for them on regular basis within a given interval. These projects, exercises, assignments and class tests were marked on time with the provision of vital remarks so that students could witness their progress and appreciate suitable remedial lessons when necessary. Marking schemes for various tests, exercises, projects, etc were constantly discussed with students to prepare them to answer examination questions.

3.12 Post Intervention

At the end of the intervention activities, students were examined on these activities. Each student was given an electrical circuit diagram on a sheet and provided with the components for them to identify, examine and construct. Theory questions based on

identification and the basic skills needed to identify were given to the students to answer for just thirty minutes. The work was collected, marked, and analyzed.

After three weeks of intervention implementation, students were given the same questionnaire used during pre-intervention for their responses. This was done to compare behaviours of students after the intervention period. One week after the administration of the questionnaire, a post intervention test of the same standard as the pre-intervention test (see Appendix B) which also lasted for 30 minutes was administered to students. This was done to compare the performance of the students before and after the intervention period to measure the efficiency of the intervention procedures. Two weeks after the test and communicating results to students, 10 students selected at random were interviewed to uncover their views and experiences about the intervention design implemented in their class.

3.13 Validity of the Main Research Instrument

The questionnaire underwent validation analysis. This was achieved by giving the instrument to colleagues to read through and offer their suggestions. Also the questionnaire was vetted by lecturers who had done in-depth research work in science education. Items in the entire questionnaire were similar for all the respondents and this enabled the researcher to cross-check some of the answers given.

3.14 Reliability of the Main Research Instrument

The reliability of the questionnaire was determined by carrying out a pilot testing, in Form two General Art 4 (2Art4) class. Fifty-seven students as well as two integrated science teachers were sampled and used for the pilot-testing. Items in the questionnaire for the science teachers were similar to those in the student's questionnaire. This was

done to enable the researcher cross-check some of the answers given by the teachers and students alike.

3.15 Data Analysis

The responses of students were organized into frequency counts after which they were converted into percentages for easy interpretation and analysis.

Qualitative and quantitative methods of data analysis were used. The data from the questionnaire and tests were analyzed quantitatively whilst the data from the observation and interview sessions were analyzed qualitatively. The results obtained from the study were analyzed in two (2) phases.

Mean values, frequencies and percentages were used in the first phase to analyze the test scores (i.e. pre-intervention test and post- intervention test) and questionnaires. On the other hand, qualitative analysis was done to find out students views and perceptions concerning the effectiveness of the intervention implemented. The interviews were audio-taped, transcribed, analyzed and noted after each interview session.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Overview

This chapter discusses and analyzes the questionnaire, pre-test and post-test scores to determine whether there has been a significant difference in the conceptual understanding of the students after the intervention. There is also a presentation on the research questions that guided the study.

4.1 Analysis of Pre- Intervention Data

This is where the data gathered during the pre-intervention stage of the research is analyzed based on the instruments used.

4.1.1 Observation

Observations before implementation of the intervention revealed that Form 2A4 students perceived integrated science as difficult and boring. Observation of students exposed some of the negative attitudes of the 2art4 students that cause poor conceptual understanding and lack of interest in the study of electrical circuits. It was noticed that, most students felt reluctant to answer questions in class as they were not ready for the lessons. Others had no interest in writing notes and doing class exercises. Although few students actively participated in the lessons others read books of their interest during integrated science lessons. Based on these behaviours of the students, it was deemed useful to initiate an interview to unveil their reason for those behaviours.

4.1.1 Interview

A separate semi-structured interviews conducted with the students. This interview was employed to find out factors that contribute to the problems students face in the learning of electrical circuits.

4.1.1.2 Students' Responses from the Interview Schedule

Students' interview provided the means for the modification of views depending on the responses to meet the desired goals. It also helped getting more information from the students. During interview sections, majority of the students complained that, they did not understand what was being taught in class. Some also said that they had no interest in the subject as it is full of theories. Others complained that text books for integrated science were boring and difficult to read and understand on their own before coming to class. Others also said, the teaching of the subject was abstract as they wanted to be involved in the process.

4.2 Findings from the diagnostic practical exercise

Despite the background information obtained through the use of questionnaire in the conceptual understanding of electrical circuits, a test was conducted to determine the conceptual understanding level in electrical circuit identification. After marking their test papers, it was found that about 70% of the students could not identify the type of electrical circuit. The remaining 30% of the students that identified the type of electrical circuits could not outline all the individual components of the electrical circuit. Out of

the 30% that identified the electrical circuits, 20% of the students outlined the electrical components from their minds or what they had seen in a book. The remaining 10% of the students that identified the type of electrical circuit were able to outline most of the individual circuit components but could not state the functions of the individual components in the electrical circuit.

In summary, the students' conceptual understanding was not the best and it reflected in the overall scores obtained in the diagnostic exercise.

4.3 Questionnaire

Questionnaire administered to Form 2A4 students at the pre- intervention stage was used to find out their attitudes towards the study of integrated science. Based on their responses it was revealed that most of these students perceived integrated science as boring and difficult. Table 2 shows their responses and percentages related to each item in the questionnaire.

Table: 2

Students Response to Questionnaire items before the intervention stage

Item number	Items	Number of Reponses				Number of respondents
		YES	%	NO	%	
1	Were you taught electrical circuits in					

	JHS?	57	100	—	—	57
2	Is the electrical circuit topic a difficult field?	39	68.4	18	31.6	57
3	Do you like studying electrical circuits?	7	12.3	40	70.2	57
4	Do you read other books in integrated science class?	23	40.4	34	59.6	57
5	Does the teacher organize practical activities for you?	—	—	38	66.7	38
6	Does the teacher use teaching and learning materials in teaching (TLMs)?	20	35.1	37	64.9	57
7	Do you pay attention in electrical circuit lesson because a lot of TLMs are used?	15	26.3	42	73.7	57

8	Has the use of hands-on activities sustained your interest in electrical circuits?	—	—	57	100	57
9	Does the teacher involve the class in the teaching process?	11	19.3	46	80.7	57
10	Are you grouped to perform various tasks during electrical circuit lessons?	—	0	57	100	57

From Table 2 above, it can be deduced that, students had no interest in the study of electrical circuits as they perceive the topic to be difficult and boring. It can also be deduced that, students were neither engaged in activities nor group work or project.

4.4 Pre-intervention test

The scores of the students during pre- intervention test have been analysed. Table 2 shows distribution of marks obtained by Form two Art four students of J.E.A.Mills Senior High School during the pre-intervention test.

Table 3

Frequency distribution of marks for the pre-intervention test

Scores	Number of students(f)	Class mid-point(x)	Fx	Percentage score (%)
0-2	5	1	5	8.8
3-5	13	4	52	22.8
6-8	17	7	119	29.8
9-11	8	10	80	14.0
12-14	9	13	117	15.8
15-17	3	16	32	5.3
18-20	2	19	38	3.5
$\Sigma f = 57$			$\Sigma fx = 443$	100

$$\frac{\Sigma fx}{\Sigma f} = \frac{443}{57} = 7.77 = 7.8$$

Mean (x) =

Statistical analysis of Table 3 above shows that 35 students, representing 61% of the total number of students scored below 10 out of 20 marks, 22 students, representing 38.5% scored half and above the total possible mark. The Table 1 indicates that, out of 57 students who took the test only 5 students representing 8.7% scored the pass mark (15)

and above. Again, the modal class is 6-8 and a mean score of 7.8 shows that the performance of the students in the pre-intervention was generally poor.

4.5 Analysis of the Post-intervention data

An analysis of the data gathered after the intervention activities based of the instruments used.

4.5.0 Observation

After implementation of intervention procedures, Form Two Art four (2A4) students' interest towards the study of electrical circuits has improved tremendously as observed. Students were mostly punctual to class and prepared for lessons, and actively involved in the teaching and learning of the topic. It was also noticed that, students developed keen interest in the study of the subject hence performed well in the post intervention test.

4.5.1 Interview

A brief analysis of the responses received from the interview conducted with the Assistant Headmistress Academic, the Science teacher and students after the intervention stage.

4.5.1.0 Post-intervention interviews with the Assistant Headmistress (Academic) and the integrated Science teacher

The two subjects above agreed that Form Two Art Four (2A4) student's conceptual understanding has improved and now they showed positive attitude towards the study of electrical circuits. Students were also seen creating and manipulating teaching and learning materials (TLMs) from the environment either to be used by the teacher or to add to what they had in their group project's works. Methods of teaching were different and

involved students. This led to better understanding of concepts hence improved on their performance than the lecture method which covers wide range of topics but yields poor result. It was agreed that using hands-on instructional approach of teaching had great influence on students' performance; it generates curiosity, positive perception and sustains the interest of learners.

4.6 Students' Responses from Interview Schedule

Students selected for the post intervention interview confessed that the use of hands-on activities was effective as they have developed interest in the study of the topic. Students disclosed that hands-on activities and project works given were useful since it enables them to discover things for themselves. They agreed that, teaching of the subject using hands-on activity that require students' participation would help develop and sustain their interest in learning the topic. Students also said they were comfortable, less tensed to learn from their colleagues; hence grouping of students is a good way of learning electrical circuits. Students also revealed that, class exercises after every lesson enabled them to assess their learning outcomes.

4.7 Questionnaire

After implementation of intervention design, the same questionnaire administered at the pre intervention stage was given to Form 2A4 students for responses. This was done to find out their interest for the subject and performance in the subject. Students' responses at this stage were positive and very encouraging.

Table 4

Students Response to Questionnaire items after the intervention stage

ITEMS	RESPONSE (YES)		RESPONSE (NO)		TOTAL NO. OF RESPONDENT S
	NO.	%	NO.	%	
1. Were you taught electrical circuits in integrated science at JHS?	57	100	0	0	57
2. Is electrical circuit a difficult content in integrated science?	11	19.3	46	80.7	57
3. Do you like studying electrical circuits in science?	7	12.3	50	87.3	57

4.Do you read other books in integrated science class?	0	0	100	100	57
5.Does the teacher organize hands-on activities for you?	57	100	0	0	57
6.Does the teacher use teaching learning materials (TLMs) in teaching?.	57	100	0	0	57
7.Do you pay attention in electrical circuit					

lessons	57	100	0	0	57
because a lot of TLMs are used?					
8.Has the use of hands-on activities sustained your interest in electrical circuits?	57	100	0	0	57
9.Does the teacher involve the class in the teaching process?	57	100	0	0	57
10.Are you grouped to perform various tasks during	57	100	0	0	57

electrical circuit lessons?					
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All items with the exception of 2, 3 and 4 had 100% ‘Yes’. Item 4 was 100%, ‘No’ which revealed that, Form 2A4 students do not read other books during integrated science lessons. Item 2 had 46 students responding No, meaning out 57 students in the class, only 11 representing 19.3% perceive electrical circuit as difficult. Item 3 revealed that 7 students representing 12.3% do not like studying electrical circuits. Careful analysis of students’ response from the questionnaire reveals that, Form 2A4 students of John Evans Atta Mills Senior High School have their interest in electrical circuits being aroused and sustained, hence an improvement in their conceptual understanding.

4.8 Post- Intervention Test

Marks obtained by students during post- intervention test have been analysed. Table 4 shows distribution of marks obtained by Form Two Art Four students of John Evans Atta-Mills Senior High School during the post-intervention test.

Table 5**Frequency distribution of marks for the post-intervention test**

Scores	Number of students(f)	Class mid-point(x)	Fx	Percentage scores (%)
0-2	0	1	0	0.0
3-5	2	4	8	3.5
6-8	7	7	49	12.3
9-11	13	10	130	22.8
12-14	6	13	78	10.5
15-17	18	16	288	31.6
18-20	11	19	209	19.3
Total:	Σf =57		Σfx=762	100

$$\text{Mean (x)} = \frac{\sum fx}{\sum f} = \frac{762}{57} = 13.37 = 13.4$$

From Table 5 above, the mean score is 13.37 and the modal class is 15-17. Out of the 57 students who took the test, 29 students representing 50.88% of them performed above

average and had scores within 15-20. This indicates that the performance of students in the post-test has generally improved.

4.9 Comparison of Pre-Intervention and the Post-Intervention Test Results

The purpose of the Post- intervention was to verify the effectiveness of the intervention on students. Table 5 below shows a comparison between the pre-intervention test analysis and the post intervention test analysis.

Table 6

Comparison of Pre-intervention and Post-intervention test results

	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention
Mean	7.77	13.37
Percentage (%)	8.7	50.88
Modal class	6-8	15-17

The percentage of students who performed well in the pre-intervention test by scoring 15 and above was 8.7% and those who did well by scoring the pass mark and above in the post-intervention test came to 50.88%. This shows that there has been a tremendous change in Form 2A4 students' conceptual understanding and performance in electrical circuits.

Comparing the mean score of the pre-test (7.77) to that of the post-test (13.37), shows that there has been a significant increase of (5.6), hence the performance of students in learning and conceptual understanding on aspects of electrical circuits has improved. Also, comparing students' performance at the pre-test to these results, it can be seen that through the use of the hands-on activities, higher number of students were able to improve their conception on electrical circuits. The student's conceptual understanding about circuit connections improved and they were able to identify and state the functions of electrical circuit components. This study agrees with the findings of Erduran (2007) and Scerri (2007). Comparing the post- intervention responses in Table 3 of items 7,8 and 9 obtained from the students to the pre-intervention responses in Table1, it can be seen that 57 students representing 100% were of the view that the use of hands-on activities had sustained their interest in the learning of electrical circuits and Table 3 also indicate that 57 students representing 100% also had the view that they were now involved in the teaching and learning process and hence pay attention in class and behave positively in class, the hands- activities in the lesson kept students active and alive in the lesson since no incidence of sleeping occurred during the teaching period. This help in improving their conceptual understanding and performance in the post-intervention test. The study supports the findings Bilgin(2006). Bilgin (2006) stated that hands on activities develop students attitudes toward science positively.

4.10 Discussion of the Results

The results analysed indicate that the performance of Form Two Art Four (2Art4) students of John Evans Atta-Mills Senior High School in electrical circuits had improved hence it appears there is change of attitudes toward the study of the topic. This is reflected in their performance in the post- intervention test. Even though only 29 students scored the pass mark and above, the improvement was substantial, since the mean score of the post-
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593562> 322

test (13.37) is greater than that of the pre-test (7.77). The study therefore supports the findings of Ünal, (2008) and Bilgin (2006). According to Ünal, (2008) Hands-on activities enhance students understanding and replace their misconceptions with the scientific ones while Bilgin (2006) stated that hands on activities develop students attitudes toward science positively.

In particular, for the study of electrical circuits, students need to explore the environment to arouse their interest, develop positive attitudes toward the subject and other related science courses. Teaching should involve the use of hands-on activities (activity- based) and instructional materials (teaching and learning materials) to assist improve conceptual understanding and sustain the interest of the students.

4.12 Presentation of the Analysed Data for Research Questions

The first objective was to use hands-on instructional approaches to improve on the conceptual understanding of second year art students on electrical circuits in J.E.A Mills Senior High School. The research findings are presented according to the research question posed to achieve this objective.

Research question 1: What difficulties do students face in the use of hands-on activities during lessons on electrical circuits?

The dominant students perception of concepts of electrical circuit is that it is difficult, tedious,

abstract, and fundamentally irrelevant. This perception makes the use of hands-on activities in teaching electrical circuits is a challenge to convince students that physics is rewarding, fun, useful, and

most of all a worthwhile endeavour. Before they take their first concept on electrical circuits,

they know little or nothing about those subjects. The teacher has to help the students to implant

fresh knowledge on the use of hands-on activities upon the palimpsests of their minds. This made

the use of the hands-on activities by the students quite difficult as some could manipulate the

circuit components but could not state their function while others too knew nothing at all.

Although they would be shocked to hear you say it, students arrive in their electrical circuit class

with a set of physical theories that they have tested and refined over years of repeated

experimentation. The reason is that students have spent some years exploring mechanical

phenomena by walking, running, throwing baseballs, catching footballs, and riding in

accelerating vehicles. They have also some more limited experience with electrical phenomena,

gained from using electric circuits in the home, and about the behaviour of light, lenses, and

mirrors. Based on their observations, students have pieced together a set of "common sense"

ideas about how the physical universe works. Unfortunately, research has shown that these "common sense" ideas are in the main incompatible with correct physics. Worse still, these erroneous ideas are robust and difficult to dislodge from students' minds, in large measure because these ideas are not addressed by conventional physics instruction. Also, 50.88% of the respondents indicated that the hands-on activities enabled them to interact with other students during the lesson while the teacher guided them to develop concepts relevant to the lesson which eliminated lack of confidence and fear in the manipulation of teaching and learning materials.

Similarly, an observation of hands-on learning noted that students' demonstrated strong communication tied to working in teams (Bass, Yumol, & Hazer, 2011). Team learning enables good students to assist the weak ones in the class thereby making the class more enjoying and interesting.

Research question 2: To what extent will the use of activity-based method improve the conceptual understanding of students in the identification of the components and the interpretation of circuit diagrams?

This can be associated to the effectiveness of the intervention strategies employed during the teaching of electrical circuits by the researcher. Hands-on activities and electrical circuit components were used during the teaching and learning process to arouse the conceptual understanding, curiosity, and to sustain the interest of the learners. The hands-on activities influenced discussions meaningfully as abstract ideas were made concrete. The students developed keen interest in the hands-on activities and began to question the teacher based on their previous ideas and opinions. In teaching electrical circuits, a lot of TLMs in addition to the electrical circuit components were used for the explanation of concepts. Students were given group work to prepare simple electrical circuits before discussion in class. This enabled them to prepare before coming to class, hence they were actively involved in the teaching and learning process. The researcher found out that students show much interest when they interact with teaching and learning materials than when they are not working with them.

The study also observed that students of different age groups perform better when they are

taught with hands-on activities and instructional materials. Hands-on activities stimulate the

various senses of the body. The researcher used a lot of hands on activities to help improve the

students' concepts on electrical circuits. And thus, help improve the conceptual understanding of

the students to learn better. The respondents indicated their preference to activity oriented

teaching (hands –on activities). In an interview, respondents stated that hands-on activities facilitate understanding and recalling of electrical circuit concepts. In a similar study (Ateş & Eryilmaz, 2011) indicated that students who experienced hands-on activities frequently (every day or once a week) had significantly higher scores of science achievement than those students who experienced hands-on science infrequently.

Research question 3: What are the views of students on the use of hands-on activities to teach electrical circuits?

Dickinson (2003) believed that, the understanding of every subject is developed through the engagement of the learners in activities. Hands-on activities, the use of TLMs and other forms of activities influence students' interest. Students confirmed that they were highly motivated to learn the concept, this was evident from their questions and answers. Table 3 revealed that all the 57 students representing 100% were of the view that the use of hands-on activities had sustained their interest in the learning of electrical circuits and Table 3 also indicate that 57 students representing 100% also had the view that they were now involved in the teaching and learning process and hence pay attention in class and behave positively in class, the hands- activities in the lesson kept students active and alive in the lesson since no incidence of sleeping occurred during the teaching period.

A variety of hands-on instructional methods coupled with positive reinforcement is an important approach in influencing students to study electrical circuits. The use of the activity method of teaching during the intervention helped to improve the conceptual understanding of the Form Two Art (2A4) students in electrical circuits (refer to Table 4, which shows a comparison between students' performance before and after the intervention).

The researcher found out that students are able understand some concepts of electrical circuits much easier when they interact with their peers in their own environment. Also, students were of the view that their understanding of certain concepts in electrical circuits has developed through their engagement with their own colleagues since they feel much comfortable interacting with themselves than with a teacher. They also made mention of the fact that the hands-on activities make them active, concentrate and therefore prevent them from sleeping in class. In a follow up interview some of the respondents stated that, conducting hands-on activities makes lesson more exciting , leads to positive motivational outcomes and facilitate understanding of concepts. This agrees with the findings of Franklin and Peat (2005) who concluded that hands-on learning provides a more realistic and exciting experience of the content. It therefore obvious from the findings of this study that there is statistical significant difference in the conceptual understanding of students when they are taught with hands-on instructional approach than when they are not taught with them.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.0 Introduction

The preceding chapter has presented the summary of results. This chapter highlights the main findings of the study and the overall study conclusions and implications of the study findings. It also provides recommendations for further study and on what needs to be done based on the identified factors responsible for the poor conceptual understanding in J.E.A Mills Senior High School, Ekumfi, Otum.

5.1 The Main Findings of the Study are as follows:

The performance of Form Two Art Four (2A4) students of J.E.A Mills Senior High School improved exceedingly when hands-on activities teaching methods, timely marking of students exercises and effective remedial lessons were conducted.

The conceptual understanding of the students increased greatly when they engaged in practical activities. Enhanced participation and performance in science were noticeable when the students were grouped to perform activities and projects. This technique enabled the students to express themselves unreservedly, share ideas, develop the spirit of team work and also learned from one another. Students developed self-confidence and freely expressed their opinions during lessons.

The uses of varied teaching methods such as hands-on activities, practical activities, peer tutoring, and discussions also made lessons interesting. This improved the students' performance in integrated science.

5.2 Conclusion

The purpose of the research was to improve the conceptual understanding of S.H.S students on electrical circuits using hands-on instructional approaches.

The performance and interest of students in electrical circuits can be greatly improved by involving them in teaching and learning process through the use of TLMs and hands-on activities. Interventions reveal that students learn better when they are involved in the teaching and learning process. They can also be put into groups to perform activities and discuss findings among themselves. These techniques would help arouse and hopefully sustain their interest in integrated science.

Although few students of Form 2A4 still had challenges in the conceptual understanding of electrical circuits, it is hoped that constant implementation of appropriate interventions would gradually help them develop positive attitudes towards the study of the subject to improve their conceptual understanding. According to Dewey, (1985), learning by doing is the corner stone of learning and that students can build knowledge by experience. Therefore, if teachers design appropriate hands-on activities for students, they will be able to overcome any problem in identification and understanding of electrical circuits.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made so that timely measures are adopted to ensure efficient teaching and learning of integrated science in our schools and to promote science education in the country.

1. Teachers of J.E.A. Mills Senior High School should design activities to involve students in teaching especially in explaining electrical circuit concepts which seem to be abstract in science.
2. Students of J.E.A. Mills Senior High School should actively participate in science activities to enhance their conceptual understanding of the subject. One's opinion and perception have a great effect on our ways of understanding and doing things, hence students are encouraged to be positive about life to enable them succeed in their endeavours.
3. Students of J.E.A. Mills Senior High School should be encouraged under the effective guidance of the teacher to explore new learning strategies that can go a long way to improve their conceptual understanding in science learning. The teacher should also avoid the use of abusive language and scolding of students in class, so as to build good and positive students-teacher relation.
4. Science teachers of J.E.A. Mills Senior High School must use different methods of teaching so as to make the learning easier, attractive and interesting to students and this would go a long way to arouse and sustain their interest and also improve conceptual understanding in the subject.
5. Teaching methods used in the teaching of electrical circuits should be flexible enough to accommodate diversity among the students. Appropriate teaching and learning materials should be used when teaching electric circuits. Grouping students making use of mixed ability groups should be encouraged to build positive student-student relation.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Research

This study focused on the use of hands-on instructional approaches to arouse and sustain the interest of S.H.S students in some aspects aspects of electrical circuits in J.E.A. Mills <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593562> 331

Senior High School in order to help improve their conceptual understanding. However, further research could be how to solve this problem by using different approaches such as;

- Peer-tutoring techniques, integrating ICT, inquiry and demonstration methods of teaching.
- Carrying out the research in other schools to uncover other causes and difficulties students face in the understanding of concepts in electrical circuits.
- Replicating the study in other schools using larger samples than that used in this study.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank the following people for their assistance during the production of this thesis:

Professor Kojo Donkoh Taale, my thesis supervisor, for his insight, enthusiasm, support and motivation;

Mr. Twumasi Ankrah Kwarteng, for the hours of discussions given without reserve which gave me the courage to continue when I felt over-whelmed;

Mrs. Rita Abena Kaburi for assisting me typing this thesis and for all his comments and suggestion, particularly on the mathematical aspect of the thesis, and my lovely siblings Mrs. Florence Abonjua and Frederick Achengkwoa. I am very grateful for everything.

The entire family of Winners chapel international, Winneba, especially to the resident pastor Pastor Raphael Nii Ayettey and my colleague pastors; Pastor Christopher Cedarleb junior and Pastor Andrews Amoah Afrifa for their prayers, invaluable time for encouragement, advice and spiritual support;

Webu Group , for their financial support.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis to the Almighty God and my beloved wife Mrs. Rita Abena Kaburi and my wonderful son Epaphras Copeland Wematu Kaburi junior.

And to my parents Mr. John Achengkwoa Kaburi and Mrs. Janet Kaburi .

APPENDIX A

PRE-INTERVENTION ACTIVITIES

OBSERVATIONAL GUIDE

Are students ready for integrated science lessons on electric circuits?

Are students fully involved throughout the lesson?

How do students answer questions in class?

How do students behave during lessons?

Are students punctual to integrated science classes?

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Semi-structured interview schedule for Assistant Headmistress (Academic) and a Science Teacher

Please tell me a little, about yourself and the subject you teach.

What was your area of specialization at the university?

What group of students perform poorly in integrated science in the WASSCE examinations?

What are the causes of the poor conceptual understanding?

How can it be improved?

Do you think the use of hands-on activity method of teaching, would help improve the conceptual of these students?

Semi-structured interview scheduled for students

What is your name?

How old are you?

What are your favourite subject(s) and why?

Do you like integrated science and other science subjects like electrical circuits?

Do you like the way science teachers teach integrated science and why?

How many class exercises, class test, and project do you do in a week?

Do your science teachers use hands-on activities in teaching?

What are the interest of Art students towards integrated science and it related courses?

What changes would you like to have in your integrated science lessons?

APPENDIX B

Questionnaire for students

This questionnaire is strictly for academic purposes. Please do not write your name on the questionnaire. The purpose of this study is to improve the conceptual understanding of students in electrical circuits. Please give candid answers to the questions. Thank you for your cooperation.

Section A

Data of students

Please tick (✓) your preferred answer

Sex: Male [] Female []

Age: 12 – 14 [] 15 – 17 [] 18 and above []

Section B

Attitude towards Integrated Science

Please answer the following questions by ticking the appropriate option.

1. Were you taught electrical circuits in integrated science at JHS?

Yes [] No []

2. Is electrical circuit a difficult content in integrated science?

Yes [] No []

3. Do you like studying electrical circuits in science?

Yes [] No []

4. Do you read other books in integrated science class?

Yes [] No []

5. Does the teacher organize hands-on activities for you?

Yes [] No []

6. Does the teacher use teaching learning materials (TLMs) in teaching?

Yes [] No []

7. Do you pay attention in electrical circuit lessons because a lot of TLMs are used?

Yes [] No []

8. Has the use of hands-on activities sustained your interest in electrical circuits?

Yes [] No []

9. Does the teacher involve the class in the teaching process?

Yes [] No []

10. Are you grouped to perform various tasks during electrical circuit lessons?

Yes [] No []

APPENDIX C

Pre intervention test on electrical circuits.

Number: **Class:** **Date:** **Time:**
40minutes

Instructions: This test consists of two parts; section A (multiple choice) and section B. (essay type) Answer all questions on this paper.

SECTION A

Which of the following is an instrument used to measure voltage in an electric circuit.

ammeter

resistor

rheostat

voltmeter

Which of the following symbols represent the S.I unit for electric current?

A

C

K

V

A device consisting of a short metal with low melting point used to protect electrical appliances from being damaged by excess current is called a

fuse

switch

resistor

thermostat

The switch or key in an electrical circuit is used for,

destroying the circuit

Making the circuit

Locking the circuit

Opening and closing the circuit

How many types of electric circuit connections do we have?

one

two

three

four

SECTION B

Show all workings on this sheet. Credit will be given for correct and clarity of responses to questions.

6. Shown here is the schematic symbol for a resistor:

What is the purpose of a resistor? What function does it perform?

[2marks]

.....

.....

.....

.....

7.Name **three** components of a simple electrical circuit. **[3marks]**

.....

.....

.....

.....

8. Briefly define an electrical insulator and give an example. **[2marks]**

.....

.....

9.A simple electrical circuit has a voltage supply of 8v. If the total resistance is 4 ohms determine the current flowing through it. **[4marks]**

.....

.....

.....

.....

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.....

.....

10. (a) state the ohm's law. **[2marks]**

.....

.....

.....

(b)Identify the following types of switches, according to their style of actuation (how each switch is physically operated):

[2marks]

APPENDIX D
Post-Intervention Interview Items

Semi-structured interview schedule for the Assistant Headmistress (Academics) and a science teacher.

What is the interest of the second year Art students this second term in relation to first term towards the study of integrated science?

What is their performance of this second term compared to the first term?

Do you agree to the assertion that using hands-on activity method of teaching and engaging students in activities would improve the conceptual understanding of students in electrical circuits, especially Art students?

What recommendation(s) would you give to teachers who teach science at the various levels of education?

Semi-structured interview schedule for students

What are some of the importance of electrical circuits?

What are your opinions about the learning of electrical circuits, is it interesting/boring/easy/difficult?

Do you think the use of hands-on activities would help improve the conceptual understanding on electrical circuits?

Do you think learning from your peers would help improve your conceptual understanding in electrical circuits?

APPENDIX E

A sample of students exercises for post intervention test

Class Test

1a. the rate of flow of electric charges known as electrons through a conductor per second is called

b. state the units of the following:

power

Energy

Electric current

Resistance

State the expression for the resistance of two conductors connected in

series

parallel

2. a. Give three examples of insulators

B. What will the light bulb do when the switch is open, and when the switch is closed?

3.a) State three practical applications of static electricity

b) Distinguish between direct current and alternating current.

c) a 6volt power packed sends a current of 2A flowing through a resistor. What is the resistance. 4mks

4. Explain how an ohmmeter is able to measure the resistance of a component (in this case, a light bulb)

when there is no battery or other source of power connected to it:

Also, identify the reading you would expect the ohmmeter to indicate if the light bulb were burnt out

(failed "open").

- a. Distinguish between electromotive force e.m.f and potential difference
- b. states the **three** sources of electrical power generation.
- c) A resistor of 10ohms has a current of 2A flowing through it. What is the potential difference across the resistor?

APPENDIX F

Marking scheme of students exercises for pre-intervention test

SECTION A

1. D

2. A

3. A

4. D

5. B **5 marks (1 mark each)**

SECTION B

6. Yes, it is a resistor. **1mark**

It opposes the flow of current in an electric circuit. **1 mark**

7. wire, bulb, key or switch, resistor, capacitor, transistor, cell, battery, voltmeter, ammeter.

(Any 3×1 for 3 marks)

8. an electrical insulator is any substance or material that does not heat or electricity to flow through it **.1mark**

Examples: plastic, rubber , polythene, dry wood, cloth, glass.etc. **(any 2 for 1mark)**

9. From the ohms law ;

V= IR **1mark**

Where, V = voltage

I = current

R = resistance

Therefore ; $I = V/R$

$I = 8/4$ **1mark**

$I = 2A$ **2marks**

10. a. Ohms law states that the current passing through a metallic in a circuit is directly proportional to the potential difference across it ends provided temperature remains constant. **2marks**

b.

- ✓ temperature key
- ✓ Toggle key
- ✓ Limit key
- ✓ Push button key (**2marks**)

APPENDIX G

Marking scheme of students exercises for post intervention test

- 1a. electric current ½ mark
- 1b.i. watt ii. Joule iii. Ampere iv. Ohms **2 marks**
- 1c. a.i. $R = R_1 + R_2$ a.ii. $I/R_1 + I/R_2$ **1mark**
1 mark
2. i)Glass ii. Rubber iii. Paper **1 mark**

ii) When the switch is closed, the light bulb will receive full voltage from the battery. When the switch is open, the light bulb will receive less voltage (and correspondingly, less current). **1 mark**

iii) Alternating current **1.5 mark**

- 3a. used in paint spraying
 Used in photocopying
 Used in dust precipitation (each ½ mark= 1.5)

3b. Differences between direct current and alternating current. **3 marks**

Direct current D.C	Alternating current A.C
Flows in one direction	Flows backward and forth
Produces a magnetic field with constant size and polarity	Produces magnetic field whose size and polarity continuously change
Does not induce emf	Induce an emf

3.c) $V = IR$

$R = V/I$ $v = 6v$; $I = 2A$

$R = 6v/2A$

$R = 3\Omega$ 2 marks

4. Ohmmeters always contain a battery or some other internal source of electrical power so that the component under test may be supplied with a small amount of current, in order to measure how hard it is for current to go through. 1marks

If the light bulb were burnt open, the ohmmeter would register an extremely large (infinite) amount of resistance. 1marks

5a. electromotive force is the force that drives electric current through the components of an electric circuit while potential difference is the energy per unit electric charge released to drive current through an electric conductor. 2marks

5b. hydro power

solar power

tidal power (each ½ mark)

5c. $V=IR$

$R=10\Omega$

$I=2A$

$V= 10\times 2$

$V=20v$ 1marks

J. E. ATTA MILLS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

STUDENT ANSWER SHEET

Name: Rebecca Baako

Date: 7/06/07

Subject title: _____

Paper: _____

Write the question number in this column

① Electrical current ✓

1/2

b i. Watts ✓

ii Energy Joules ✓

iii Ampere ✓

iv Ohm ✓

2

bi $R_t = R_1 + R_2$ ✓

1

iv $\frac{1}{R_t} = \frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2}$ ✓

1

Q2 Wood ✓

iii plastics ✓

iv Book ✓

1

B

When the switch is closed, when the switch is ^{closed} opened the light bulb would be switch on that is there would be flow of electric current through the circuit

Write the question number in this column

Question Number

Write on both sides of the paper

Page No

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When the switch is opened
When the switch is opened the light bulb ~~would~~ would not have switch on since there is no flow of electrical current through the circuit.

Q3

- ① For pressing of clothes
- ② For switching on bulb (electric bulb)
- ③ For charging phones

④ Direct current is a current which has only one direction while alternating current is a current which continuously changing its direction of flow.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{d) } V &= IR \\ \frac{6}{2} &= \frac{2R}{2} \\ R &= 3 \text{ ohms} \end{aligned}$$

Q4

Ohmmeters ~~are~~ always contain a battery or some other internal source electrical power so that the components under test may be supplied with a small amount of current, in order to measure how hard it is for the current to go through.

⑤ If the light bulb were burnt open the ohmmeter would extremely large

Part Four

7/06/2017

Rebecca

Baako

amount of resistance

Q5

Electromotive force is the voltage drive of a cell. ~~the voltage difference is the voltage drop across a circuit~~ (1)

(A) Hydroelectric power

(B) cells or batteries (1 1/2)

(C) P-V solar cells

$$G = V = IR$$
$$V = 2(10)$$
$$V = 20V$$

(1)

18/20

J. E. ATTA MILLS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

STUDENT ANSWER SHEET

Name: NGORABENWASITIE BISMARCK

Date: 1th July 2019

Subject title: INTEGRATED SCIENCE

Paper: _____

Write the question number in this column

1. (a) Electric Current (2)

(b) Power - Watt

Energy - Joule

Electric current - amp Ampere (1)

Resistance - Ohm

(c) (i) Series - $R = R_1 + R_2$ (1)

(ii) Parrallel - $R = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2}}$ (1)

2. (a) Plastics, Wood and Book. (1)

When the switch is open there is no current flowing through it and when it is closed there is current flowing through it

3. (a) pressing of clothes. (2)

(b)

Alternatively current has a sinusoidal waves while Direct current has a direct waves-

Write the question number in this column.

Question Number _____

Write on both sides of the paper

Page No _____

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3. (c) $V = IR$
 $G = 2(R)$
 $\frac{G}{2} = \frac{2R}{2}$
 $3 = R$
 $\therefore R = 3 \Omega$

4. (a) Ohmmeters always contain a battery or some other internal source of electrical power so that the component under the test can be supplied with small amount of current, so that it can measure how hard the current to go through.

→ If the light bulb were burnt open the ohmmeter can register its own resistance.

5. (a) Electromotive force is the force that drives electric current through the component of a circuit.

(b) Solar, sunlight and water

(c) $V = IR$
 ~~$V = 20 \times$~~
 $V = 2 \times 10$
 $V = 20 \text{ volts.}$

2 ARI 4
J. E. ATTA MILLS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

STUDENT ANSWER SHEET

Name: ISSAH FATIMA
 Subject title: Integrated Science

Date: 7th July 2017
 Paper: TWO (2)

question number in this column

- ① D ✓
 - ② A ✓
 - ③ A ✓
 - ④ D ✓
 - ⑤ B ✓
- 4

6. Show here is the schematic symbol for a resistor
 Ans Yes a resistor. ✓

What function does it perform?
 Ans A resistor is any material that opposes electric current to pass through them. it. ✓

- 7. (i) Resistor ✓
 - (ii) Switch ✓
 - (iii) Bulb ✓
- 3

8 Electrical insulator is a substance which does not allow light to pass through them. eg! rubber, plastic

⑨ $I = \frac{V}{R}$ ✓

$= \frac{8}{4} = 2$

$\therefore I = 2A$ ✓

4

Write the question number in this column

Question Number

Write on both sides of the paper

Page No

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Q. Ohm's law state that when the temperature of a conductor is constant, the potential difference is proportional to the current flowing in a resistor

Q. Identify the following types of switches according to their style of actuation (how each switch is physically operated).

A - Temperature

B - Toggle

C - Button

D - Push

1/2

18 1/2
/ 10

3 ART 4

J. E. ATTA MILLS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

STUDENT ANSWER SHEET

Name: Emmanuel K Mensah

Date: 7/07/17

Subject title: Inter. Science

Paper: _____

Write the question number in this column

1a Electric current

12

b Power → Watts

Energy → Joules

Electrical current → Ampere

Resistance → Ohm

2

c Series = $R = R_1 + R_2$

Parallel = $R = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2}}$

4

2 Rubbers, words and Bulbs

b

When the current is a switch is open, there will be no current flow through the electrical circuit.

When the switch is closed there will be current flow through the electrical circuit.

3a Pressing of clothes

4

Write the question number in this column

Question Number 3
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Page No

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3b Direct current is an electrical current which flows in only one direction whereas alternatively current is an electric current which continuously change its direction of flow by moving forwards and backwards.

3c $V = IR$
 $G = 2(R)$
 $\frac{G}{2} = \frac{R}{2}$
 $R = 3\Omega$

2
12/20

4a Ohmmeter has a battery within it and source of electrical power so that component under test can be supplied with small amount of current so that it can measure how hard the current to go through it.

5a Electromotive force is the force that drives electric current through the component of a circuit.

b Water, solar and sunlight

c $V = IR$
 $V = 2 \times 10$
 $V = 20 \text{ watts}$

1

2 ARTS 4

J. E. ATTA MILLS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

STUDENT ANSWER SHEET

Name: ABBAN MICHAEL
 Subject title: INTEGRATED SCIENCE

Date: 7/07/17
 Paper:

Write the question number in this column	
	SECTION A
1.	d ✓
2.	a ✓
3.	a ✓
4.	d ✓
5.	b ✓

5

SECTION B

6. Shown here is the schematic for a ~~transistor~~^{resistor?}

~W~

Ans: Yes
 What function does it perform?

Ans: A resistor opposes the flow of electric current through it.

- 7.
- i. Fuse ✓
 - ii. Resistor ✓ (3)
 - iii. Transistor ✓
 - iv. Capacitor ✓

8. Electrical insulator is a substance that does not allow electricity to pass through it. (1)

Examples: Plastics, wood, stones and rubber

9. Voltage = 8v
 Resistance = 4ohms
 Current = ?

Write the question number in this column.

Question Number Write on both sides of the paper

Page No

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$$V = IR$$

making I the subject,

$$\frac{V}{R} = \frac{IR}{R}$$

$$I = \frac{V}{R}$$

$$\therefore I = \frac{8}{4}$$

$$I = 2A$$

4

10. Ohm's law states that the current through a conductor is proportional to the potential difference across it provided its temperature remains constant.

10.6. Types of keys.

- Ans. (a) Toggle keys ✓
(b) Temperature keys ✓
(c) Pushbutton keys ✓
(d) Limit keys ✓
(e) Float keys ✓

11

17/20

About the Author:

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Mphil. Science Education

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